

Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways

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Abbreviations list

(ma)DMP (machine-actionable) Data Management Plan

EOSC European Open Science Cloud

FAIR Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

IRA Interoperability Reference Architecture

PTA Plan-Track-Assess

RDA Research Data Alliance

RDM Research Data Management

SKG Scientific Knowledge Graph

Executive Summary

Pilots are important to the overall success of OSTrails serving as the foundation for co-designing, testing solutions and demonstrating the benefits of adopting our proposed Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) framework. They reflect the varied Research Data Management (RDM) practices across Europe, addressing unique challenges in different research contexts. Deliverable 4.1 introduces the methodology and operational processes for implementing the **15 national** and **8 thematic** as well as the **Horizon Europe** pilots. Each pilot will contribute to at least one, but in most cases to several of identified use cases/topics, based on their needs (which are described in this document for each pilot).

As regards **national pilots**, all of them will be developing maDMP templates tailored to national funder requirements and local infrastructure. These templates aim to streamline RDM processes, enabling researchers to manage their data effectively in compliance with funder guidelines. Several pilots are working to integrate DMP tools with national infrastructures, including CRIS (Current Research Information Systems), repositories, and other data services. A core focus for pilots in Spain, Poland, France, and Germany is improving the FAIRness of research data. These pilots are developing or testing FAIR evaluation tools, establishing FAIR metrics, and assessing how to ensure data is accessible, interoperable, and reusable across different platforms and systems. Many pilots aim to increase collaboration between national stakeholders, such as universities, funders, and research infrastructures. By fostering better interoperability between systems, the pilots help to reduce the administrative burden on researchers and improve the quality and accessibility of research outputs. Several countries, including Serbia and Greece, are focused on enhancing repository and CRIS systems by linking DMPs with other research outputs, such as datasets and publications. Pilots across the project are actively testing and evaluating RDM tools and services. These include the implementation of maDMP tools like ARGOS, integration with lab notebooks and the FAIR assessment of digital objects in repositories.

The **thematic pilots** in the OSTrails project are strategically chosen to represent a diverse range of scientific domains and organisational contexts, within which they will validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the methodologies, tools, and frameworks developed in the project. Thematic pilots implement the OSTrails framework occurs through the following activities:

- Development of Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans: pilots like PaNOSC and ENVRI/JERICO are actively working on enhancing DMP templates to support this transition
- Development and integration of Scientific Knowledge Graphs: Pilots such as SSHOC/CLARIN are focused on extending existing data catalogues into SKGs
- FAIR Assessment Tools: For example, the ESCAPE/ObsParis pilot is working on adapting FAIR assessment criteria to the requirements of the astronomy community,
- Testing and implementing the interoperability standards developed within OSTrails, inter alia also for participation in EOSC

- Continuous feedback to the OSTrails development teams in the technical work packages 1-3

Through its **Horizon Europe** Pilot, OSTrails will contribute to advancing the discovery and further exploitation of DMPs produced and delivered by EC grant beneficiaries. The aim is to:

- Publish DMPs as FAIR outputs and connect them with other research outputs, such as data or publications generated by projects.
- Assess the FAIRness of described outputs as well as of the DMPs' content in adherence to the EC's Research Data Management policy.

To achieve that, the OpenAIRE Graph that is regularly synced with CORDA will be utilised and assisted by ARGOS and the FAIR Validator services to implement the proposed OSTrails PTA framework. This pilot is closely associated to the DMP evaluation service that is developed in WP3 and to the policy brief that is synthesised in WP6 where a detailed analysis report on current DMPs in HE projects and a proposed updated DMP template for FP10 are expected to be delivered.

Our methodology follows a granular approach to ensure effective communication and information exchange at different levels, from intra pilot to cross pilot and cross work package activities coordination.

The goal of **intra-pilot coordination** is to ensure that each national and thematic pilot operates efficiently with clear role allocation and regular communication. This process is primarily self-organised within the pilots, with clear roles and tasks being allocated within each pilot, based on the task description of the Description of Work. Each pilot has regular internal meetings to discuss progress, challenges, and strategies, keeping all partners aligned with timelines and objectives. Reporting takes place within the overall EU project reporting and in the dedicated meetings of national and thematic pilots described below.

Inter-pilot coordination aims to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange between national and thematic pilots and across pilots. This process includes:

- National Pilots: Monthly meetings for national pilot representatives to share updates, challenges, and successes, with a structured agenda covering technical work package developments, tool testing, and cross-pilot learning.
- Thematic Pilots: A Thematic Pilots Coordination Committee (TPCC) will oversee progress, discuss challenges, and ensure alignment with the OSTrails framework.

Thematic and Horizon Europe pilots will participate in a joint session with the national pilot meetings at least twice a year to share updates and collaborate on joint issues.

Cross-work package coordination ensures that technical developments from WP1-3 are integrated into the pilots and that pilots provide valuable feedback for further improvement. This process includes:

- Early Involvement of Pilots: Engaging pilots early in the development process ensures solutions are aligned with the pilot's needs, allowing feedback loops for refinement.
- Regular Updates and Feedback: Pilots provide feedback to technical WPs (WP1, WP2, WP3), ensuring developments are informed by practical experience and tested solutions.
- Deliverable Presentations: WP5 organizes meetings where deliverables are presented once finalized, allowing broader dissemination and feedback from the consortium.

The deliverable is structured as follows: **Section 1** provides background information to the project's structure, objectives and results and makes the connection with the pilot activities. **Section 2** explains the methodology of the survey performed in order to capture the latest pilots' landscape and use cases that are detailed in **Section 3** (the template used to collect input from the pilots is in the Annex). **Sections 4 and 5** provide more in-depth view to each of the national and thematic pilots' plans, and Horizon Europe pilot is mentioned in **Section 6**. Then, **Section 7** explains how coordination is achieved within and across pilots and other project activities.

1. Overview of the OSTrails project and the pilots

1.1. Background

A set of guidelines that emphasise the use of data by machines, the **FAIR Principles** (Findability, Accessibility Interoperability and Reusability), have become *de facto* the global norm for good Research Data Management (RDM) practices, a prerequisite for replicability and reproducibility. However, the current fragmentation and inefficiency in managing data hinders the progress of research practices. Research Infrastructures struggle to create an interconnected landscape.

The adoption of FAIR Principles is promising, especially in today's research practices that involve an increasing amount of Artificial Intelligence related activities. For data to be FAIR, the following limitations should be addressed and overcome.

- ***Findable:*** Data is often fragmented in different locations and often not indexed or documented in a way that makes it easily discoverable. Researchers may struggle to locate relevant datasets.
- ***Accessible:*** Data silos can restrict access to data, limiting who can view or use the data.
- ***Interoperable:*** Inconsistent data formats and metadata standards hinder the ability to integrate and analyse data from different sources. Interoperability is crucial for combining datasets from various disciplines to advance research.
- ***Reusable:*** For data to be reusable, it must be well-documented and stored in a way that preserves its context and provenance. Fragmented data often fail to meet these criteria, reducing the potential for data reuse in future research.

1.2. The "Plan – Track – Assess" Framework

Against this background, the EU-funded OSTrails project¹ (Grant agreement ID: 101130187) will work collaboratively with 40 partners and 23 national and thematic pilots to transform data management, establish interoperable knowledge graphs, and deliver modular FAIR tests, with the ultimate goal of providing a comprehensive solution to drive FAIR research practices forward. OSTrails recognises the diverse landscape and fosters a collaborative approach to enhance traceability and evidence-based evaluation of research.

¹ see also <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101130187>

The terms "Plan," "Track," and "Assess" (PTA) refer to the three key activities of the project's **"PTA Framework"**² that together form a comprehensive approach to enhancing the planning, monitoring, and evaluation of scientific knowledge production:

- Plan: The "Plan" stage focuses on increasing the efficacy of Data Management Plans (DMPs) by transforming them from static documents into dynamic, interconnected, and machine-actionable resources. The aim of OSTrails is to make DMPs a central tool for improving the quality and FAIR-compliance of Research Data Management (RDM) practices across scientific domains. This involves developing templates, guidelines, and tools that support researchers and institutions in creating and maintaining DMPs that are both compliant with funding requirements and tailored to the specific needs of their research activities.
- Track: For the "Track" phase, the project aims at establishing an open, interoperable, and high-quality ecosystem of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). These SKGs will be enriched to become tangible evidence of the implementations of the FAIR principles carried out by different scientific communities. This involves linking data, publications, datasets, software, and other research outputs in a way that makes their management and accessibility more efficient. The tracking phase aims to monitor the research lifecycle effectively, from data creation and processing to publication and reuse, facilitating the implementation of FAIR principles at every step.
- Assess: The "Assess" component aims to deliver modular and extendable FAIR tests towards "machine-actionable" metrics complemented by user guidance embedded in tools. The FAIR tests can be implemented at any stage of the research life cycle to assist researchers, research support personnel, funding organisations, and publishers in improving the quality of RDM for any research product. Assessment tools and services developed under this component will help evaluate the FAIRness of digital objects, ensuring that they meet the criteria established for findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

² See (Reichmann et al., 2024)

Figure 1. OSTrails - Plan, Track, Assess (PTA) Framework.

Collectively, these key activities form the OSTrails Commons - a suite of methods, tools, services, guidance, and training designed to provide end-to-end solutions for realising FAIR principles throughout the research lifecycle.

1.3. The role of the pilots

The national and thematic pilots play an important role in OSTrails: they are the means through which new methodologies, tools, and standards are tested and validated in real-world use-cases. The 15 national and 8³ thematic pilots provide a wide array of contexts, including different national and thematic infrastructures. They serve as case studies and proof-of-concept instances that demonstrate the viability and benefits of the OSTrails framework.

- Testing and Validation in Real-World Contexts: The pilots provide empirical evidence of the effectiveness of OSTrails' outputs. By implementing the developed methodologies and tools in real-world scenarios, the pilots help identify practical challenges and gather user feedback. This iterative process ensures that the

• ³ At the proposal stage, there were 9 thematic pilots. T4 involved CLARIN, CESSDA, PaNOSC in a cross-domain pilot that aimed to standardise thematic metadata for FAIRness across clusters. This pilot was discontinued, and its outputs will become available in the context of WP3 activities following the CLARIN-led clusters' coordination meetings.

solutions are robust, user-friendly, and capable of addressing the actual needs of researchers and institutions.

- Diverse Contexts for Comprehensive Testing: The variety of contexts represented by the pilots ensures that the OSTrails framework is applicable across different research environments. National pilots focus on integrating OSTrails specifications into local infrastructures, developing machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) tailored to national funders' requirements and local data infrastructures. Thematic pilots, involving organisations from ESFRI clusters and other thematic research communities, test the alignment of OSTrails methodologies with domain-specific requirements and practices.
- Case Studies and Proof-of-Concept: Successful pilots provide case studies that demonstrate the viability and benefits of the OSTrails approach. These examples showcase how OSTrails can enhance research data management (RDM) practices, ensure compliance with the FAIR principles, and improve the overall quality and transparency of research.
- Co-defining Metrics and Standards: As part of the use cases (see below), the pilots contribute to co-defining metrics for DMP evaluation and FAIR assessment. The metrics are tailored to align with national funder policies and the specific needs of thematic research communities. By involving stakeholders in their development, the pilots help ensure that the evaluation criteria are relevant, practical, and widely accepted.
- Community Engagement and Training: By working closely with researchers, data stewards, and institutional support staff, the pilots help disseminate best practices, provide hands-on training, and foster a culture of continuous improvement in RDM. This engagement contributes to building the capacity of research communities to adopt and sustain the innovations introduced by OSTrails.
- Scaling and Sustainability: By demonstrating the impact and benefits of OSTrails in diverse settings, the pilots pave the way for its adoption at a larger scale. The lessons learned and best practices identified through the pilots help refine the tools and methodologies, ensuring they are scalable and adaptable to different research contexts.
- Implementation: Work Package 4 (WP4) is dedicated to the design, implementation, and oversight of the national and thematic pilots, as well as the Horizon Europe Pilot. Task 4.1 Pilot Coordination runs through the whole duration of the project and provides the groundwork for Task 4.2 (implementation of the national pilots, start: M18) and Task 4.3 (implementation of the thematic pilots, start M18) as well as Task 4.4. (Horizon Europe Pilot, start: M13). WP4 ensures that the pilots align with the project's objectives and contribute valuable insights and feedback to refine the project's outputs.

In summary, the national and thematic pilots provide evidence to support the widespread adoption of OSTrails outcomes. As part of the use cases, the pilots can contribute to co-defining metrics for DMP evaluation and FAIR assessment, tailored to national (funder) policies and thematic communities. Through these pilots, OSTrails contributes towards creating a robust, interoperable, and FAIR-compliant ecosystem for research data management, driving improvements in the quality, transparency, and impact of scientific research. The pilots are designed and implemented in WP 4.

2. Use Cases

2.1. Methodology

WP4 has initiated its activities by organising separate meetings for national and thematic pilots. The objectives of these meetings were to update the pilots on the project's progress. Vice versa the national pilots provided updates about their status in the initial stage of the project. For national pilots these meetings have been held on a monthly basis.

For both national and thematic pilots, the aim was to initially identify a) the respective pilots' ecosystem in which they operate and b) the use cases/topics that they intend to work on. To achieve this, a survey was conducted through an excel file (also available online), with two main worksheets:

- *worksheet 1* - overview of use cases/topics with the aim to elicit from each pilot whether they are at the time of writing: a) sure that they will cover a use case b) uncertain that they will cover a use case, c) sure that they will not cover a use case and d) other options, such as covering a use case through their own resources ("in kind").
- *worksheet 2* - 26 structured questions covering the participating organisations' policies and activities regarding RDM and FAIRification, as well as the wider national or thematic community in which they operate

At the time of writing, all partners have returned the filled in survey, although there is variation in the length and completeness of the answers received.

We also integrate, where relevant and available, results from interviews with national pilots conducted as a dissemination activity (in WP5) and the updates of planned and/or conducted activities in national pilots from the monthly national pilots' meetings.

3. The six topics

In the project proposal, six key use cases/topics for the pilots are identified, each addressing important aspects of research data management:

I. Develop maDMP templates to address national funders and local infrastructure (PIDs, CRIS, repositories)

Current DMP platforms can export DMPs to PDFs and maDMPs following RDA recommendations on DMPs. The maDMPs will facilitate automated and dynamic data management processes, helping researchers to comply with funders' policies and making it easier for institutions to manage research data life cycles effectively. However, the current state of play does not guarantee that all the requirements of the local funders can be covered, or that local infrastructure is sufficiently taken into account. In this use-case national pilots would thereby develop extensions to the maDMP specification.

This use case goes well together with use case V and VI, because this template will be needed for automated assessment.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP1, WP2

II. Extend repositories for archiving maDMPs and create links and relations (qualified references) between archived DMPs and publications

Data Management Plans (DMPs) are traditionally in a narrative form and often exist as static documents. These DMPs, while required by many funders, are not readily interoperable or actionable. The link between DMPs and publications is limited, and DMPs in their current form do not facilitate monitoring and assessment at scale. OSTrails therefore aspires to transition DMPs from static documents to living, interconnected resources that are FAIR by design.

This use case is particularly interesting for those partners wanting to extend their repository with (ma)DMPs and use the information that maDMPs carry about RDM activities and outputs to link to other related deposited objects and PIDs. For example, maDMPs can provide information on related datasets (cross-references as defined in FAIR principles). Such cross-references can be made to objects you have in your system or outside, as long as it is a PID.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP1, WP2

III. Interoperate with the OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs to enhance qualified references with publications (incl. Pre-prints, open peer reviews), DMPs, maFAIRTests, data, workflows, instruments, software

The current landscape of SKGs is fragmented, which makes interoperability critical. OSTrails will work to overcome semantic and syntactic heterogeneity and diversity in

coverage which are significant barriers to the integration and interlinking of content from various sources.

This use case is therefore of interest to any project partner interested in connecting existing repositories, DMP platforms, FAIR assessment tools or other systems to knowledge graphs. An example can be connecting a local repository to OpenAIRE SKG.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP2, WP3

IV. Co-define FAIR metrics for funders, institutions and research communities and/or assess deposited DO's and repositories

There is a move toward expanding FAIR Principles to various research outputs and developing metrics and maturity indicators to measure compliance with FAIR Principles. OSTrails deals with FAIR assessment and harmonisation of how FAIR is evaluated. This use case is about defining a set of metrics that can be used to measure the FAIRness of digital objects deposited in repositories and/or using the project tools to measure FAIRness of repositories' outputs.

This use case is of interest to any partner wishing to develop FAIR metrics based on the requirements of their funder, institution or research community. The metrics will be used by the project's FAIR assessment services. The framework, format of the metrics, services, etc. will come from WP3.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP3

V. Co-define DMP evaluation criteria and assess DMPs quality according to national policy and criteria

A number of funders have established DMP evaluation rubrics, such as⁴

- The Science Europe Guide (<https://scienceeurope.org/our-resources/practical-guide-to-the-international-alignment-of-research-data-management/>)
- The NWO DMP Assessment rubric (<https://zenodo.org/records/3629157>) and
- The FWF Evaluation Rubric (https://www.fwf.ac.at/fileadmin/Website/Dokumente/Ueber_uns/Aufgaben_und_Aktivitaeten/Open_Science/fwf_dmp_evaluation_rubric.pdf).

This use case aims to extend testing and assessment beyond strictly FAIR principles, particularly to measure the degree to which a research project complies with its DMP objectives (depending on the specific project).

The work will be based on the WP 3 service for automated DMP assessment, and the use case will revolve around customising the tool from WP3 to local needs. This use case

⁴ Personal knowledge of the author. For a comprehensive overview see (Science Europe, 2020), in particular table C, page 25.

requires a maDMP template from topic 1 and communication with the respective funder to provide input on the evaluation criteria.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP3

VI. Extend national monitoring systems and funder’s reporting systems with maDMPs

This use case is aimed at integrating machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) into broader research management and reporting ecosystems both inside the research institutions as well as at the funders’ side. It involves including (ma)DMPs indicators in monitoring dashboards, as well as convincing national funder(s) to accept maDMPs following the RDA/OSTrails specification in addition to simple text documents such as PDFs, and should this be made available by their software, integrate with their reporting system, at least as a pilot. Funder cooperation is important for this task.

Other relevant work package interactions: WP1, WP2

4. National Pilots

The OSTrails project incorporates 15 national pilots designed to tailor and validate the project's methodologies, tools, and standards in specific national contexts. These pilots will ensure the practical applicability and relevance of OSTrails across different research environments. Figure 2 provides an overview of the national pilots, with the coordinating organisation for each country.

1-Croatia Rudjer Boskovic Institute	2-Greece Hellenic Academic Libraries Link members, Athena RC	3-Netherlands SURF	4- Norway Sikt	5-Serbia U Belgrade
6- Austria- Uni Wien, TU Wien, Tu Graz	7-Poland PSNC, U Warsaw/ICM	8-Ireland TU Dublin	9-Portugal, UMinho & FCT	10-France INRIA
11-Finland CSC	12-Germany RWTH Aachen	13-Spain FECYT	14-Czech Republic, CTU	15-Sweden U Göteborg

Figure 2. National Pilots Overview.

Below we start by providing an overview of which national pilots focus on which use cases and then discuss for each national pilot the state of play and their respective ecosystem and their implementation plans.

4.1. Use Case/Topics Coverage Overview

Each national pilot will contribute to at least one, but in most cases several of the use cases/topics identified above. The survey results show strong involvement across various use cases and activities, indicated by (x – certain participation). There are also cases of uncertain participation (?). This indicates areas where participation is still under discussion or where pilots are selectively involved in particular activities. These entries highlight opportunities for refining and potentially increasing the engagement of these pilots as the project evolves. In some instances, pilots have also been clear that they will not cover a specific use case/topic, indicated by (o). This shows that while these pilots are contributing, their engagement is limited to other use cases. The results are depicted in figure 3 overleaf (in landscape format for better readability).

The following **Error! Reference source not found.** quantifies this information, per use case:

Table 1. National Pilot Participation Per Use Case.

TOPIC/USE CASES	FULL PARTICIPATION (x)	No PARTICIPATION (o)	UNCERTAIN PARTICIPATION (?)	OPTIONAL IN KIND	OTHER COMMENTS
I	15	0	0	0	0
II	7 to 8	1	4 to 5	0	1
III	4	4	4	2	1
IV	5	3	3	2	0
V	5 to 6	5	2 to 3	1	1
VI	2	9	3	0	2 for ?

For the following graphical representations (**Figure 4** and **Figure 5**), the numbers have been rounded to 0,5 in cases where there were varying options for use cases (use case II and V).

Topics (Description of Work)	1-Croatia Rudjer Boskovic Institute	2-Greece Hellenic Academic Libraries Link members, Athena RC	3-Netherlands SURF	4- Norway Sikt	5-Serbia U Belgrade	6- Austria- Uni Wien, TU Wien, Tu Graz	7-Poland PSNC, U Warsaw/ICM	8-Ireland TU Dublin	9- Portugal, U of Minho, FCT	10-France (INRIA)	11- Finland CSC	12-Germany RWTH Aachen	13-Spain FECYT	14-Czech Republic, CTU	15-Sweden U Göteborg
I develop maDMP templates to address national funders and local infrastructure (PIDs, CRIS, repositories);	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
II extend repositories for archiving maDMPs and create links and relations (qualified references) between archived DMPs and publications;	x	x	extending repos for archiving DMPs is not explicitly in our proposal; creating links & relations is part of (III) below	?	x	x	x	?	x	?	? x	x	o	?	x
III interoperate with the OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs to enhance qualified references with publications (incl. Pre-prints, open peer reviews), DMPs, maFAIRTests, data, workflows, instruments, software;	x	interoperability with OpenAIRE Graph	x	?	?	optional in kind	x	?	o	o	o	optional in kind	o	x	?
IV co-define FAIR metrics for funders, institutions and research communities and assess deposited DO's and repositories;	o	x	x (assuming FIPs count here)	?	x	optional in kind	partially (we provide FAIR assessment service for DOs)	o	x	x	o	optional in kind	?	x	?
V co-define DMP evaluation criteria and assess DMPs quality according to national policy and criteria	o	x	o	?	x	x	partially (we aim to generate DMP report according to national policy and criteria)	x	x	o	? x	optional in kind	o	o	?
VI extend national monitoring systems and funder's reporting systems with maDMPs	o		? (TBD, possible in final year of project)	x	o	o	o	o	o	?	? we will observe this	o	x	o	o

Figure 3. Results of Survey Worksheet 1.

Figure 4. Levels of Participation per Use Case.

Figure 5. Overall level of full, no, uncertain or in-kind participations.

4.2. N-1: Croatian National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-1. Croatian National Pilot
Key organisations	Ruđer Bošković Institute (RBI) provides RDM support to the Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ) and their researchers for HRZZ funded projects, through services like data management planning tools, the national repository infrastructure Dabar (with more than 150 institutional and/or thematic repositories), and the national CRIS system called CroRIS.
Objectives	<p>Led by RBI, the Croatian National Pilot focuses on three main areas:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Translating requirements from the national funder, the Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ) into machine-actionable DMPs using Argos 2. Enhancing the workflow to archive DMPs into the national repository (Dabar), which is currently possible only for PDFs and 3. reporting about DMPs in the national Current Research Information System (CroRIS).
RDM Policy Implementation Status	Currently, there is no comprehensive RDM policy at the national level or within HRZZ, although DMPs are mandatory for HRZZ-funded projects. The pilot is committed to reinforcing FAIR principles by enhancing national open science e-infrastructure and advocating for open science policies at both national and institutional levels. RBI is also actively involved in the EOSC Association and OpenAIRE AMKE, participating in the development of national infrastructure.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	The pilot is committed to reinforcing FAIR principles by enhancing national open science e-infrastructure, developing and promoting open science policies at national and institutional levels, and advocating for these policies within HRZZ and the Croatian Ministry of Science, Education and Youth. Efforts are

	underway to include open science activities in Croatia's evaluation process and to implement a national open science policy.				
Involvement in EOSC	RBI is an Observer in the EOSC Association and an OpenAIRE AMKE member, participating in the development of national infrastructure.				
Affiliation with National Funders	Collaboration with the Croatian Science Foundation (HRZZ) on developing a maDMP in ARGOS and designing an open science policy.				
Description of Activities	<p>One of the significant challenges identified is the lack of tools for creating maDMPs tailored to HRZZ projects, and the absence of DMP registration and metadata records in CroRIS. To address these gaps, the pilot aims to develop functionality for pushing maDMPs from the DMP tool to local repository infrastructures like Dabar and CroRIS systems.</p> <p>The pilot involves extensive collaboration with HRZZ to develop maDMPs in compliance with national requirements and to integrate these plans into the broader national infrastructure. DMPs will be archived in digital repositories within the Dabar, with additional metadata descriptions.</p> <p>The pilot will also implement records about DMPs in CroRIS and establish connections between DMPs and other related records within CroRIS. The expected outcomes include providing the Croatian academic and research community with tools for creating maDMPs, improving the infrastructure for storing maDMPs, and linking DMPs with other research objects. This will enhance transparency and accessibility of research data.</p> <p>The pilot has established communication channels with the national librarians' network and users and administrators of the national e-infrastructure, ensuring broad stakeholder engagement and support.</p>				
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<p>1 maDMP template for funder</p> <p>100 researchers engaged</p>				
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pilot activities</th> <th>Timeline</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Implemented 1 maDMP template for funder</td> <td>End of 2024/beginning of 2025</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pilot activities	Timeline	Implemented 1 maDMP template for funder	End of 2024/beginning of 2025
Pilot activities	Timeline				
Implemented 1 maDMP template for funder	End of 2024/beginning of 2025				

100 researchers engaged	Starting from the end of 2024 or the beginning of 2025 until the end of the project	
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4.3. N-2: Greek National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-2. Greek National Pilot
Key organisations	HARDMIN is the national university data repositories infrastructure, connected to the Hellenic Data Service - HELIX. It serves as the federated environment for data deposits across 15 Greek Universities and implements policies for Research Data Management and Open Science at institutional and national levels. Heal-Link is the Greek National Library Consortium serving 15 Universities and implements policies for Research Data Management and Open Science at institutional and national levels. Athena Research Centre (ARC) is a leading Research and Innovation Center on big data management, analytics and applied AI, located in Greece, employing more than 500 persons.
Objectives	The Greek national pilot builds on the partnership between HEAL-Link and ARC to support the HARDMIN federated infrastructure, providing data repositories across 15 Greek universities. It aims to implement policies for Research Data Management (RDM) and Open Science connected to the Hellenic Data Service - HELIX. The pilot will enhance interoperability with the OpenAIRE Graph, connect HEAL-Link scholarly infrastructure services (such as PIDs) with the ARGOS-GR DMP platform, develop maDMP templates, and assess the FAIRness of selected universities within the HEAL-Link consortium.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	HEAL-Link and ARC are key members of the Hellenic Open Science Initiative (HOSI) and have published the National Open Science Plan in 2020. They are in the process of self-adopting it in their local settings, with the University of Patras currently adopting an institutional policy. The HARDMIN data policy is followed for data deposits by Greek and Greek-affiliated researchers.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	HEAL-Link and ARC aim to enhance the adoption of FAIR principles by creating customised and machine-actionable DMP/dataset templates that fit Greece's local policies, infrastructures, and community needs. This includes linking DMP templates with institutional/national/thematic data

	<p>services and organisations, providing training on FAIR principles, developing monitoring mechanisms, and creating feedback loops for continuous improvement.</p>
<p>Involvement in EOSC</p>	<p>ARC is a member of the EOSC Association, participating in numerous EOSC projects and representing Greece in the EOSC Steering Board. Through HOSI, pilot members support national representation and contributions to EOSC.</p>
<p>Affiliation with National Funders</p>	<p>The pilot has support from the General Secretariat for Research and Innovation (GSRI), with ARC maintaining close collaboration to support Open Science policy adoption in Greece.</p>
<p>Description of Activities</p>	<p>The Greek national pilot, led by HEAL-Link and ARC, aims to address several local infrastructure gaps and enhance the research data management ecosystem in Greece. One significant gap is the lack of connection to Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), which limits the interoperability and integration of research data. Additionally, the current version of the ARGOS tool used for Data Management Plans (DMPs) is outdated and not yet connected to other HEAL-Link and ARC services. Furthermore, while there is a need for alignment with the minimum FAIRness model, this alignment has not yet been fully achieved.</p> <p>To provide end-to-end solutions, the pilot will focus on developing APIs and standards for information exchange, as well as implementing FAIR metrics, tests, and assessment outputs. The local community requires a DMP Evaluation Service configured to meet institutional and national criteria, supporting the General Secretariat for Research and Innovation's (GSRI) future policy for national projects.</p> <p>Currently, HEAL-Link performs manual assessments focusing on bibliometrics, while ARC maintains a demo monitor for GSRI projects using the OpenAIRE Graph. The pilot plans to use user requirements and feedback to guide the testing and evaluation of methods, tools, and services. However, at present, there is no interaction with SKGs.</p> <p>The development of maDMP templates will be undertaken through consultations with the HEAL-Link community and GSRI. For archiving maDMPs, the PID infrastructure of HEAL-Link will</p>

	<p>be employed to provide DMP-IDs, although the exact method has not been decided yet.</p> <p>The co-definition of FAIR metrics will involve engaging stakeholders, including government agencies, funding bodies, academic institutions, and researchers, to develop coordinated and comprehensive policies and standards for FAIR data implementation. The FAIRness of deposited digital objects (DOs) and repositories will be assessed using the FAIR Validator of OpenAIRE.</p> <p>The expected outcomes of the pilot include improved workflows for research data management, enhanced communication among researchers and stakeholders, and increased FAIR outputs and practices in the national research ecosystem.</p>										
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<p>1 maDMP template</p> <p>43 member institutions; 15 FAIR assessed digital objects</p>										
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th style="background-color: #e6e6fa;">Pilot activities</th> <th style="background-color: #e6e6fa;">Timeline</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>maDMP template implementation</td> <td>Early 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Selection of HARDMIN digital objects and selection of institutional repositories that will be engaged</td> <td>Early 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Organize webinars for researchers to present DMP tool, emphasize the interoperability of published DMPs with other systems, and encourage the creation and publication of DMPs that meet both institutional and funder requirements.</td> <td>Early 2025 until the end of the project</td> </tr> <tr> <td>FAIR assessed digital objects</td> <td>Early 2025 until the end of the project</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pilot activities	Timeline	maDMP template implementation	Early 2025	Selection of HARDMIN digital objects and selection of institutional repositories that will be engaged	Early 2025	Organize webinars for researchers to present DMP tool, emphasize the interoperability of published DMPs with other systems, and encourage the creation and publication of DMPs that meet both institutional and funder requirements.	Early 2025 until the end of the project	FAIR assessed digital objects	Early 2025 until the end of the project
Pilot activities	Timeline										
maDMP template implementation	Early 2025										
Selection of HARDMIN digital objects and selection of institutional repositories that will be engaged	Early 2025										
Organize webinars for researchers to present DMP tool, emphasize the interoperability of published DMPs with other systems, and encourage the creation and publication of DMPs that meet both institutional and funder requirements.	Early 2025 until the end of the project										
FAIR assessed digital objects	Early 2025 until the end of the project										

4.4. N-3: Dutch National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-3. Dutch National Pilot
Key organisations	<p>SURF is a cooperative association of Dutch educational and research institutions that collaborates to develop and acquire advanced digital services, fostering continuous innovation and knowledge sharing. The Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS) is an interdisciplinary research institute at Leiden University (LU) whose mission is to improve how science is practised and governed and how it serves society; the aims of the Centre’s research include contributing to the adoption of open science practices as well as to innovations in open research information and research analytics. The Dutch Research Council (NWO) is one of the most important science funding bodies in the Netherlands and its mission is to advance world-class scientific research; included in the NWO Strategy 2023-2026 is a specific ambition to encourage the transition to Open Science. In addition to these three partners that were originally named in the OSTrails proposal, the N-3 Dutch National Pilot consortium now also includes in-kind support and collaboration from TU Delft, Utrecht University, VU Amsterdam, and the DCC-PO, the national knowledge centre for research support and infrastructure across the Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Encode</i> current university/RPO-approved and funder-specific DMP templates into existing maDMP tooling/platforms, beginning with Argos ● <i>Elicit</i> requirements and workflows of different research communities, and develop domain/discipline-specific maDMP guidance and, where appropriate, maDMP templates that respond to currently unmet user needs/preferences ● <i>Embed</i> FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) into maDMP templates, focusing on a subset of more ‘FIP-mature’ domains in which they can be most readily and meaningfully implemented

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Enrich</i> maDMP templates with Persistent Identifiers ('PIDification'), mapping sections of maDMPs to relevant PIDs and flagging maDMP fields that may be suitable for future PIDification • <i>Interoperate</i> maDMP templates (via PIDs) by reusing information upstream and downstream and making it actionable for 1 or 2 to-be-determined use cases • <i>Extend</i> local/national graph(s) with maDMPs, and interoperate with e.g. the Netherlands Research Portal and the OpenAIRE Graph
RDM Policy Implementation Status	All the Research Performing Organizations (RPOs) involved in the project have RDM policies.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Both SURF and the involved RPOs are committed to promoting and strengthening the uptake of FAIR principles. The pilot will explore how RDM practices and infrastructures can be made more FAIR, focusing on sustainable and open research data management.
Involvement in EOSC	SURF is a EOSC Mandated Organisation, involved in EOSC-ENTRUST, FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC (e.g., RAiD, MSCR, DTR) and the development of a national EOSC node. NWO is a member of the EOSC Association. CWTS is a collaborator on another EOSC project, GraspOS.
Affiliation with National Funders	NWO has written a letter of support for the OSTrails NL National Pilot, and they regularly consult with them about the project's status and to elicit feedback. NWO has a rubric for DMP evaluation currently in place but is also considering updating their data management/open science policy which will be informed by the results of this pilot and the overall OSTrails project.
Description of Activities	The pilot has identified significant gaps in local infrastructure. Not all RPOs have a DMP tool in place, and there is no national Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) that directly harvests from repositories. While there are some thematic FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) and self-assessment tools developed by DANS, a comprehensive infrastructure is still

	<p>lacking. This gap presents a challenge in standardising and improving data management practices across institutions.</p> <p>One of the main areas of interest across Dutch RPOs is developing integrated workflows that combine DMP, privacy, and ethics documentation within a single environment. This approach is somewhat different from the central OSTrails focus on 'machine actionability,' indicating that the adoption of maDMP tooling will depend on the development of interoperability standards to integrate PID-based maDMP tooling with locally developed workflows.</p> <p>The pilot aims to answer critical questions regarding the appropriate scope of DMPs, such as whether they should cover only data and software or extend to other outputs, how to address discipline-specific needs, and the granularity of information required by RPOs and NWO for assessing outputs. This exploration will help tailor the maDMP templates to meet the specific needs of the Dutch research community.</p> <p>Scaling up the use of FAIR Implementation Profiles is a key deliverable, aligned with a GO FAIR Foundation fellowship undertaken by team members from Leiden. This effort primarily targets natural and life sciences, leveraging the varied expertise within the national consortium in assessment methods across different domains.</p> <p>The pilot will test and evaluate the usability and usefulness of ARGOS and DSW tools within participating RPOs. It will focus on integrating FAIR Implementation Profiles within maDMP environments. The testing of services will depend on the state of infrastructure at the time of pilot kick-off, with ongoing communication of findings to key stakeholders.</p> <p>The pilot will work closely with NWO and various RPOs to adjust existing DMP templates and develop new ones, particularly domain-specific templates and associated guidance. Initially, the project will use stand-alone tools like ARGOS and DSW, acknowledging the current lack of comprehensive infrastructure to support widespread maDMP integration.</p> <p>The infrastructure for archiving DMPs is heterogeneous across Dutch RPOs. Some institutions register DMPs with local CRIS systems, while others store DMPs in non-FAIR-aligned local</p>
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	<p>storage solutions like SharePoint. There is a need to improve the linking of DMPs with research outputs across the RDM ecosystem.</p> <p>The pilot plans to develop FAIR metrics using dialogical methods, such as walk-throughs, interviews, and focus groups with key stakeholders, primarily focusing on researchers. Surveys or questionnaires may also be conducted depending on available expertise.</p> <p>The pilot will use the NWO rubric, mapped to the Science Europe DMP rubric, as a basis for evaluation. RPOs typically have institution-specific templates aligned with the NWO rubric but often more exhaustive, including privacy and ethics-related questions. Evaluations generally involve consultations between researchers and data stewards before submission to the sponsor (NWO).</p>						
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 maDMP templates; one for NWO and one for Leiden University 4 RPOs and their researchers engaged						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th data-bbox="204 1111 718 1151">Pilot activities</th> <th data-bbox="718 1111 1369 1151">Timeline</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td data-bbox="204 1151 718 1191">2 maDMP templates, incl. funder</td> <td data-bbox="718 1151 1369 1191">Mid 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td data-bbox="204 1191 718 1267">4 RPOs and their researchers engaged</td> <td data-bbox="718 1191 1369 1267">End 2025</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pilot activities	Timeline	2 maDMP templates, incl. funder	Mid 2025	4 RPOs and their researchers engaged	End 2025
Pilot activities	Timeline						
2 maDMP templates, incl. funder	Mid 2025						
4 RPOs and their researchers engaged	End 2025						

4.5. N-4: Norwegian National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-4. Norwegian National Pilot
Key organisations	The Research Council of Norway, Sikt is a public administrative body under the Ministry of Education and Research that currently develops a new joint CRIS and publication repository and has a list of data services, such as DMP service, to support the research data management of the Norwegian research community. The Norwegian national pilot involves Sikt and the National DMP working group
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop ma-templates for the Norwegian research community. Configure and link templates with the new joint CRIS system and publications repository • Extend the new joint CRIS system and publications repository with entities and PIDs and interoperate with the OpenAIRE Graph. • Assess FAIRness of data archive digital objects. • Co-define DMP evaluation criteria with the Research Council of Norway • Enhance the OA Barometer with links to publications, DMPs, data and software.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	The main Norwegian funder (RCN) published its current RDM policy in 2017 (https://www.forskningsradet.no/en/research-policy-strategy/open-science/research-data/) and the Norwegian government published its national strategy in 2018 (https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/national-strategy-on-access-to-and-sharing-of-research-data/id2582412/). As it stands, most major Norwegian RPO's have an RDM policy and DMP's are mandated.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Sikt is committed to supporting and enhancing the principles of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) by providing services that support digitalization, data sharing, and open research for education and research institutions in Norway.

<p>Involvement in EOSC</p>	<p>SIKT is involved in EOSC activities, contributing to the broader European efforts in open science and data management.⁵ EOSC Association representatives include Jan Meijer and Bodil Agasøster (for ESS ERIC). SIKT is also involved in the EOSC</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health Data Task Force - (Sigma 2, i.e. daughter company of Sikt): Long Term Data Retention Task Force - Technical and semantic interoperability: Task Force (Jan Meijer: will probably be in an expert group for financial sustainability) <p>Other EOSC-related EU projects we take part in are:</p> <p style="padding-left: 40px;">Ended in 2024 (2): EOSC Future; WorldFAIR Ongoing (1): FAIR-IMPACT Starting up in 2025 (2): FIDELIS; CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC</p>
<p>Affiliation with National Funders</p>	<p>Sikt and the Research Council of Norway (RCN) collaborate and work together on several tasks, topics and projects. In connection with OSTrails they aim to come up with, and implement, a plan for better integration of Sikt and NRC systems and services. Additionally, we aim to establish DMP templates aligned with both RCN and community needs.</p>
<p>Description of Activities</p>	<p>The Norwegian OSTrails Pilot is currently in the planning phase. The pilot will aim to enhance the interoperability of research data management systems across Norway, with a particular focus on integrating services to facilitate better data sharing and streamline workflows for researchers. The ultimate goal is to improve the data flow and accessibility of tools and services, making them easier for researchers to use.</p> <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u></p> <p>The primary infrastructure challenge identified in this pilot is the lack of integration between various services. Addressing this gap is a key focus of the pilot.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services</u></p>

⁵ See also <https://sikt.no/en/omrade/research-data>

	<p>The pilot is currently evaluating DMP tools, with input from a national working group to ensure they meet the needs of the Norwegian research community.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs:</u></p> <p>Several services within the pilot plan to utilise the OpenAIRE Graph for enriching research data. The new national CRIS (Current Research Information System) and publication repository will serve as an OpenAIRE data provider, further enhancing data interoperability.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates</u></p> <p>The pilot will focus on developing machine-actionable DMP templates through collaboration with the national funder, the established national DMP working group, and the broader research community.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u></p> <p>The process for archiving machine-actionable DMPs is still under planning.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u></p> <p>The pilot will build on the previous work of the Norwegian national FAIR-principles working group to co-define FAIR metrics, ensuring that the data management practices adhere to these principles.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u></p> <p>This aspect is currently under planning as part of the pilot.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u></p> <p>The criteria for evaluating DMPs are also under planning and will be defined as the pilot progresses.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u></p> <p>At present, open access monitoring is conducted annually and reported to both the ministry and the national funder. The pilot may build on these existing systems to enhance reporting capabilities.</p>
<p>Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)</p>	<p>1 maDMP template; 50 Institutions and their researchers engaged.</p>

Pilot activities	Timeline
maDMP template	by 2025
Community, institution and researcher engagement	by end of project

4.6. N-5: Serbian National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-5: Serbian National Pilot
Key organisations	University of Belgrade prepares the Serbian research community for data management following the European requirements relating to research data found in the project application forms of the national Science Fund.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) template tailored to the national funder, the Science Fund. This template will be developed using the Argos tool, enabling researchers to upload finalised DMPs into their institutional repositories and the national Current Research Information System (CRIS). • Assess interoperability between Argos and four designated repositories, allowing researchers to draft DMPs in Argos and establish connections between DMPs, datasets, and publications. • Integrate DMPs and datasets within the national CRIS system, eNauka, enhancing linkages between researcher profiles, publications, datasets, and organisations.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	There is currently no national or funder RDM policy in Serbia. DMPs are mandatory for projects funded by the Serbian Science Fund. Serbia's national policy on Open Science was adopted in 2018, recommending but not mandating open access to research data.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	The pilot is committed to enhancing effective RDM practices and strengthening adherence to FAIR principles in Serbia.
Involvement in EOSC	Some members of the University of Belgrade's Computer Centre are active in EOSC developments.

Affiliation with National Funders	<p>The pilot will collaborate with the national funder, the Science Fund, on the design of the DMP template.</p>
Description of Activities	<p>The pilot will address several critical aspects of research data management (RDM) and interoperability within Serbia's research infrastructure.</p> <p>As an outcome, the research and academic communities in Serbia, along with the national funding agency, will benefit from a tool that facilitates the creation of machine-actionable DMPs using templates tailored to the funder's requirements. This tool will also enable the deposition of these plans in repositories and the establishment of meaningful connections with other research outputs. Additionally, stakeholders will gain tools to assess research results for FAIR compliance.</p> <p>Key activities include:</p> <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps</u></p> <p>The current infrastructure lacks a standardised DMP template that aligns with the funder's requirements. While Argos has been translated into Serbian, it does not have an adequate template to meet these needs. Additionally, institutional repositories in Serbia, primarily built on DSpace, lack the functionality to assess the FAIRness of digital objects. Furthermore, there are no established links between DMPs, repositories, and the national CRIS system, and there is a need for clear metrics and criteria for evaluating DMPs and digital objects (DOs).</p> <p><u>Development of Required Components for End-to-End Solutions</u></p> <p>The pilot will develop and implement the necessary functionality to enable the pushing and sharing of DMPs from the Argos tool to institutional repositories and the national CRIS eNauka. This will involve creating robust integration pathways to ensure that DMPs are effectively linked with other research outputs.</p> <p><u>Addressing Local or Community Requirements</u></p> <p>The pilot will focus on embedding fully functional tools or services within CRIS or repositories, with a particular emphasis on enabling these systems to assess the FAIRness of research outputs. This is a critical need for the local research community,</p>

as current tools and services do not fully support these functions.

Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs

The Serbian research community has limited experience with using assessment tools for evaluating the FAIRness of digital objects and DMPs. Although tools like F-UJI are known, they have not been integrated into existing workflows. The pilot will address this by testing and implementing such tools within the research infrastructure.

Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs

The pilot will leverage existing interactions with OpenAIRE, as the four repositories designated for testing are already compatible with OpenAIRE guidelines for institutional and thematic repositories. Metadata from these repositories is harvested by OpenAIRE, and each DO without a DOI is provided with a Handle permalink, ensuring broader accessibility and compliance with international standards.

Development of maDMP Templates

Argos will be used as the primary tool for creating maDMP templates, which will be tailored to meet the specific requirements of the Serbian Science Fund. These templates are essential, as there is currently no recommended DMP template from the national funder.

Archiving of maDMPs

The maDMPs generated through the pilot will be archived in institutional repositories. Initially, these DMPs will be stored in PDF format.

Co-definition of FAIR Metrics

The pilot will actively engage with relevant stakeholders, including the national funder, universities, research institutions, and researchers, to define and establish FAIR metrics.

Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories

Currently, there are no established criteria for evaluating the FAIRness of deposited DOs and repositories. Through the pilot,

	<p>tools and procedures for FAIR assessment will be developed and implemented.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria</u></p> <p>There are no established criteria for evaluating DMPs in Serbia at the moment. For the moment the evaluation is guided by Science Europe's "Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management." The pilot will work towards establishing criteria, using these existing guidelines as a foundation, and adapting them to the local context and funder requirements.</p>
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 maDMP templates, incl. domain specific; 100 researchers engaged; 200 FAIR assessed digital objects.

Pilot activities	Timeline
consultations with Serbian Science Fund and the University of Belgrade and design of the maDMP templates	end of 2024
FAIR assessment of the four institutional repositories (Cherry, CER, DAIS and VinaR)	beginning of 2025
integration of DMPs in repositories and mapping them to national CRIS - eNauka. Creating relations of DMPs with other research results, and testing and refinement of maDMP templates with selected research groups	2025
dissemination and demonstration activities - trainings for researchers, students, librarians and other interested stakeholders in utilising our DMP template, and live-online demo of pilot activities for researchers and national funder	from beginning of 2025 until the end of the project (M36)

4.7. N-6: Austrian National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-6: Austrian National Pilot
Key organisations	<p>Graz University of Technology (TU Graz) is an Austrian technical university known for its strong focus on science and technology, providing advanced research infrastructure and promoting FAIR data principles including their participation in projects like FAIR Data Austria. TU Wien is a technical university in Austria with a strong commitment to research data management. The University of Vienna (Uni Wien) is one of Europe's oldest and largest universities involved in the project through its library staff as well as the institutional repository PHAIDRA and AUSSDA - The Austrian Social Science Data Archive.</p>
Objectives	<p>Three Austrian universities—TU Graz, TU Wien, and Uni Wien (including AUSSDA and PHAIDRA) collaborate to enhance DMP support. Activities in the pilot include extending, aligning and integrating DMP tools, enhancing DMP support to researchers, supporting data stewards in creating discipline-specific DMPs, providing further support implementing RDM policies, promoting FAIR principles and assessing their implementation in digital objects, as well as contributing to national and international initiatives.</p>
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<p>Uni Wien has implemented an RDM policy that outlines the responsibilities of both researchers and the university. Researchers are advised to create and maintain DMPs that detail how data will be collected, documented, stored, and shared. The university supports researchers by providing necessary infrastructure, training, and resources, including access to data repositories such as PHAIDRA and AUSSDA, ensuring long-term preservation and accessibility of research data.</p> <p>TU Wien released an institutional RDM policy in 2018, establishing a central support unit for research data management, providing data stewardship services by an interdisciplinary team.</p> <p>TU Graz implemented an institutional RDM policy in 2020, followed by the development of discipline-specific RDM policies.</p>

<p>Commitment to FAIR Principles</p>	<p>Uni Wien actively promotes FAIR principles through extensive RDM services, workshops, training, and the use of repositories like PHAIDRA and AUSSDA to ensure data is findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. They emphasise open science, transparency, and reproducibility in research, providing a bespoke training program for data stewards.</p> <p>TU Wien supports FAIR principles by incorporating them into the DAMAP tool for creating DMPs, providing a repository (called TUWRD) for persistent identifiers, standardised licences, and machine-readable formats. They offer workshops and courses integrating FAIR principles.</p> <p>TU Graz adheres to FAIR principles across all research outputs, contributing to projects like FAIR Data Austria. They provide tools and repositories for FAIR data management and a marketplace for FAIR/RDM-related projects.</p>
<p>Involvement in EOSC</p>	<p>Uni Wien, a member of the EOSC Association since 2020, is actively involved in a number of EOSC-related projects and task forces, both nationally and internationally, including major EU projects like EOSC BEYOND and EOSC Future. TU Wien has been engaged from the early stages through its involvement in the EOSC Secretariat, participating in a number of EOSC projects and contributing to national initiatives. TU Graz, member of the EOSC Focus project consortium, works towards aligning the technical development of EOSC. All three organisations are members of the EOSC Support Office Austria (the operational branch of the Austrian Mandated Organization).</p>
<p>Affiliation with National Funders</p>	<p>Researchers at the three universities frequently apply for grants and project funding through the Austrian Science Fund (FWF), the <i>Forschungsförderungsgesellschaft</i> (FFG) and other bodies like ERC and Horizon Europe. However, these funders are not structurally involved in the pilot.</p>
<p>Description of Activities</p>	<p>In the Austrian national pilot, the participating universities—TU Graz, TU Wien, and Uni Wien—are collaboratively working to enhance Data Management Plan (DMP) support and improve RDM practices. A primary focus of the pilot is to extend, align, and integrate existing DMP tools to better serve researchers and data stewards. This involves supporting data stewards in creating discipline-specific DMPs and providing extensive RDM</p>

services, including feedback and consultancy tailored to funders' requirements.

Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:

Uni Wien supports researchers in complying with DMP requirements, offering FAIR assessments for part of its data holdings using the F-UJI tool. However, there is no established workflow to assess the FAIRness of DMPs comprehensively. The university's repositories offer endpoints for third-party harvesting, such as OpenAIRE. TU Graz currently operates two tools, DAMAP for Data Management Plans and InvenioRDM for repository needs, with PURE linking authors to research outputs. TU Wien operates a local instance of DAMAP for creating machine-actionable DMPs. TU Wien also runs an institutional data repository (TU Wien Research Data Repository - TUWRD).

Required Components for End-to-End Solutions:

While specific requirements are still being determined, TU Graz notes the absence of SKGs and FAIR-assessment tools. There is a need for integrated workflows that combine DMP, privacy, and ethics documentation within a single environment.

Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements:

Uni Wien provides consultancy services on DMPs tailored to funders' requirements, with final assessments typically conducted by the funding agencies. TU Wien provides these services as well.

Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs:

At Uni Wien, feedback is provided by support staff through mail, phone, and personal meetings. Although no formal assessment tools are currently used, the aim is to develop discipline-specific templates within the OSTrails project. TU Wien provides the equivalent support and organises workshops for DMP writing where feedback is provided directly.

Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:

Uni Wien plans to develop and test discipline-specific templates to better meet the needs of researchers. TU Wien takes part in the implementation of the DMP Evaluation service in WP3 and

will deploy a local instance to offer automated feedback to the users of DAMAP.

Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs:

Content from Uni Wien is harvested by the OpenAIRE graph, facilitating broader visibility and accessibility of research outputs. Datasets from the TU Wien Research Data Repository (TUWRD) are also harvested by OpenAIRE, DataCite, and BASE.

Development of maDMP Templates:

TU Graz uses the DAMAP tool to export DMPs to FWF and Science Europe templates, which are compatible with RDA recommendations on maDMPs. TU Wien uses DAMAP. DAMAP can export non-machine-actionable templates for FWF, Science Europe, and Horizon Europe. It exports maDMPs following the RDA recommendation for maDMPs. The plan is to incorporate funder specific extensions to maDMPs, so that maDMPs better overlap with funder requirements.

Archiving of maDMPs:

At Uni Wien, PHAIDRA offers archiving of DMPs where they can be linked to publications and other outputs, though this is not mandatory. TU Graz archives DMPs in its local repository, specifying locations for data access during the research phase and long-term storage. TU Wien Research Data Repository (TUWRD) has a dedicated content type for archiving DMPs.

Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:

Currently, there are no plans from Uni Wien or TU Graz to co-define FAIR metrics with funding organisations or within their institutions. TU Wien: this depends on the requirements of the DMP Evaluation service and required customizations to reflect the needs of the university and of national funders.

Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:

Uni Wien has participated in FAIR assessments of its data holdings using the F-UJI tool and in a FAIRimpact assessment challenge. TU Graz plans to develop evaluation methods during the project, benefiting from the expertise of the OSTrails consortium. TU Wien takes a different approach and focuses on improving the quality of machine-readable descriptions

	<p>provided by the automatically rendered landing pages to ensure high compliance with FAIR principles for objects deposited into the TU Wien Research Data Repository (TUWRD).</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u></p> <p>Uni Wien uses specific criteria to evaluate DMPs, including data description and collection, documentation, metadata, ethics and legal compliance, storage and backup, data sharing and access, archiving, and preservation. These criteria align with national policies set by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF). TU Wien uses requirements of the given funder to evaluate DMPs. The ambition is to define levels of compliance, so that the evaluation goes beyond basic “is this good enough for my funder” use cases, and to focus on useful advice that makes management of data easier and better, i.e. to inherently profit the researchers.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u></p> <p>Uni Wien uses PURE as its Current Research Information System (CRIS) to support monitoring and reporting. TU Graz also employs PURE for these purposes.</p>
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 maDMP templates; up to 12 universities/research organisations/research infrastructures and their researchers engaged ; 1500 FAIR assessed digital objects

Pilot activities	Timeline
KPI: Creation and deployment of 2 machine-actionable Data Management Plan (maDMP) templates.	
Initial design of maDMP templates based on funder and institutional requirements	Months 18-22
Pilot testing of maDMP templates with select researchers and institutions, including DAMAP at TU Wien and TU Graz	Months 23-26
Final adjustments and rollout of the maDMP templates	Months 27-30
Final deployment and evaluation of maDMP templates across participating universities	Month 31

KPI: Engagement of up to 12 universities/research organisations/research infrastructures and their researchers in the pilot, promoting the use of maDMPs and enhanced Research Data Management (RDM) practices.	
Start introducing and rolling out pilot maDMP templates (See also KPI above)	Months 23-26
Expand the adoption to other universities	Months 25-28
Provide comprehensive support to onboard additional universities	Months 29-32
Review engagement rates and feedback from the universities involved	Months 33-36
KPI: FAIR assessment of at least 1,500 digital objects across institutional repositories at TU Graz, TU Wien, Uni Wien, and associated repositories (e.g., PHAIDRA, AUSSDA) using F-UJI and other metrics	
Set up and test FAIR assessment tools, including F-UJI, across the participating organisations	Months 18-21
Assessment to cover 1,500 digital objects	Months 22-30
Provide reports on findings and ensure repository updates based on the assessments	Months 31-34
Summarize FAIR assessments, reporting on repository practices	Months 35-36
Technical Infrastructure Upgrades and System Integration	
AUSSDA will upgrade its repository software to increase its F-UJI FAIR metric score	Months 18-21
TU Wien will identify groups of researchers for whom DAMAP integration could be beneficial and develop specific use cases	Months 22-25
TU Wien and other partners will implement DAMAP integrations with laboratory systems and repositories	Months 26-30
Review the effectiveness of the integrations and collect feedback to ensure optimal implementation of live, machine-actionable DMPs	Months 31-36

4.8. N-7: Polish National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-7: Polish National Pilot
Key organisations	<p>PSNC (Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center): Pilot lead, Argos-PL (Pionier) service provider, ROHub (RO-Crate) service provider, integration of Argos-ROHub, FAIROs-ROHub, national repositories-ROHub, and PIONIER.ID operator. ROHub is a research object management platform supporting the preservation and lifecycle management of scientific investigations, research campaigns and operational processes. It is developed according to the RO-CRATES framework and supports integrations with other services, such as the ARGOS-PL. ICM (Interdisciplinary Centre for Mathematical and Computational Modelling): Provider of national research data repositories (RepOD, RDS, MX-RDR), integration of national repositories with Argos.</p> <p>NCN (National Science Centre): National funding agency providing support, requirements, and evaluation of results.</p>
Objectives	<p>The goal of this pilot is to support the creation and maintenance of maDMPs in Poland. It involves managing the research data lifecycle from the perspective of researchers, data providers, and stakeholders, ensuring data is handled appropriately throughout and beyond the research project. This pilot will enable stakeholders to actively manage data and DMPs as needs evolve.</p>
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<p>As part of this pilot, the DMP tool Argos is being connected with ROHub (RO-Crate management platform, see above), allowing DMPs to be exported in various formats. An initial export to generate DMP reports according to NCN (national funding agency) format has been implemented.</p>
Commitment to FAIR Principles	<p>The pilot aims to support the adoption of FAIR principles through the use of RO-Crates, which provide rich descriptions of research projects, including resources and contextual entities. RO-Crates in ROHub are already connected to OpenAire SKG, facilitating FAIR assessments and enhancing discoverability and usability of research data. National data repositories run by ICM enable the sharing of research data according to the FAIR principles.</p>
Involvement in EOSC	<p>Pilot members are actively involved in EOSC developments, participating in a number of working groups and task forces. PSNC leads two of the three lots implementing the EOSC EU node and supports national EOSC developments, including organising EOSC-related events. ICM coordinates the University of Warsaw's activities regarding participation in the EOSC</p>

	<p>Association. It has participated in many EOSC-related projects - recently in OpenAIRE Nexus, FAIRCORE4EOSC, EOSC Future, SciLake, CRAFT-OA, and EOSC Beyond. As a member of the Open Science Agora Consortium, it will be involved in providing professionally managed services for the core components of the EOSC EU Node.</p>
<p>Affiliation with National Funders</p>	<p>The pilot is in contact with NCN, which is interested in the pilot's development and provides input regarding requirements and expectations.</p>
<p>Description of Activities</p>	<p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u> There is a national need to support the creation of maDMPs. The current system used by the national funding agency is general, inflexible, and does not provide machine-readable support. ROHub integrates Argos to support the creation of RO-Crates from DMPs, enabling FAIR assessments and connections to the OpenAire SKG.</p> <p><u>Required Components for End-to-End Solutions:</u> The pilot connects DMP tools, FAIR assessment, and SKGs with ROHub, leveraging Pionier (PL IT infrastructure and services), Argos-PL (Pionier), ROHub (EOSC/Pionier), ICM repositories (RepOD, RDS, MX-RDR), FAIROs, and OpenAire SKG. This comprehensive integration supports the dynamic management of resources related to DMPs.</p> <p><u>Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements:</u> There is a need to support the assessment of FAIRness of resources, enhance resource discoverability, and ensure dynamic management of resources related to DMPs. The pilot enables this through the integration with RO-Crates, which facilitate comprehensive and contextual management of research outputs.</p> <p><u>Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs:</u> The pilot integrates the FAIROs service, which leverages the FUJI tool and other existing services, into ROHub to enable the FAIR assessment of RO-Crates and their aggregated resources. This provides a robust method for evaluating the FAIRness of research outputs.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:</u> The pilot plans to evaluate its services with the support of NCN, ensuring that the tools and methodologies meet the needs of the national research community and comply with funder requirements.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs:</u> ROHub is already integrated with OpenAire SKG, exposing RO-Crate collections and other resources such as Jupyter notebooks and data cubes. The pilot plans to extend this integration to</p>

	<p>include other collections, enhancing the visibility and interoperability of Polish research outputs within EOSC.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> The pilot will develop maDMP templates addressing national requirements, with input from NCN. This will be supported by the integration of Argos,ROHub, and the national research data repositories,enabling the export of DMPs to meet national system requirements.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> maDMPs are archived in ROHub as RO-Crates, which include links to publications and other research outputs, ensuring comprehensive and contextual preservation. Information about maDMPs can be included in the metadata of datasets in the national research data repositories.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> The pilot plans to follow NCN's FAIR requirements and leverage the FAIROs tool to support the implementation and assessment of these metrics.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u> Using FAIROs integrated into ROHub, the pilot will assess the FAIRness of digital objects (RO-Crates and aggregated resources). The pilot will not assess the FAIRness of repositories but aims to assess the FAIRness of datasets in the repositories.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u> The pilot follows NCN's DMP requirements to ensure alignment with national policies, providing a standardised approach to DMP evaluation.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u> ROHub will be able to generate DMP reports according to national requirements, enhancing the integration and utility of DMPs in national monitoring and reporting systems.</p>
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<p>KPI 1: 1 maDMP Template Developed⁶</p> <p>KPI 2: 4 Institutions/Universities and their researchers engaged</p> <p>KPI 3: FAIR Assessment of 1000 Digital Objects</p>
Pilot activities	Timeline
KPI 1: Initial Design Phase	Month 18-21
KPI 1: Testing and Validation	Month 21-24
KPI 1: Finalise Templates	Month 24
KPI 2: Initial Engagement: outreach to research institutions, with a focus on introducing the benefits of maDMPs	Month 18-21

⁶ Modified to reflect that the National Science Centre is the only funding agency in Poland with specific DMP requirements, and thus the focus of the Polish pilot.

KPI 2: Expanding Engagement: Host workshops and webinars to train researchers on how to use the maDMP templates in their workflows	Month 21-27
KPI 2: Full Adoption	Month 27-36
KPI 3: Integrate the FAIROs tool into ROHub to enable the FAIR assessment of digital objects in national repositories	Month 18-21
KPI 3: Initial FAIR Assessments: Begin assessing the first 500 digital objects in RepOD, RDS, and MX-RDR repositories	Month 21-27
KPI 3: Scaling Up FAIR Assessments: Continue to assess a total of 1000 digital objects for FAIR compliance by the end of the project	Month 27-36

4.9. N-8: Irish National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-8: Irish National Pilot
Key organisations	TU Dublin represents the TU NET partnership of the five technical universities in Ireland (TU Dublin, Munster Technological University (MTU), Southeast Technological University (SETU), Atlantic Technological University (ATU) and Technological University of the Shannon (TUS)) who have joined efforts to provide guidance and tools for Open Science, RDM, and research in the national academic and research communities.
Objectives	The Irish national pilot aims to implement the ARGOS tool on a shared service basis across the five technological universities in Ireland. This initiative will act as a proof of concept for a shared services model for research infrastructure on a national basis. The pilot prioritises the alignment of metadata, increased interoperability, and enhanced data quality. Additionally, it will explore the integration of ARGOS with local Current Research Information Systems (cRIS) through the use of APIs. The pilot will also develop ma-templates for the TU-NET DMPs, including configuring and linking templates with the TU-NET portal

	(including all five repositories). Furthermore, the pilot will apply the FAIR principles at the level of the Irish consortium.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	This project will serve as a foundation for implementing Research Data Management (RDM) policies across the participating institutions. The delivery of RDM infrastructure via this pilot will underpin these policies.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	The pilot is committed to strengthening FAIR principles and their application in Irish organisations. The increased oversight of DMPs through Argos will enable improved support for good RDM practices, leading to enhanced FAIR compliance. The adoption of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs), integration with cRIS, and overall improvement of the RDM ecosystem are expected to significantly boost FAIR principles.
Involvement in EOSC	All members are members of the EOSC Ireland Association, but limited active engagement, due to limited national activity at present.
Affiliation with National Funders	There is no formal affiliation with national funders for this pilot.
Description of Activities	<p>The pilot aims to establish a connected ecosystem of DMP tools, FAIR assessment services, SKGs, and national digital repositories. This will support the creation and maintenance of maDMPs, facilitating compliance with national requirements and enhancing research data management practices across Ireland's technological universities.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs:</u> TU-NET institutions have a shared repository via the CONNECT platform, with all repositories being harvested into the OpenAIRE ecosystem. All institutions are represented in the Irish National Open Access Monitor. The pilot will explore including maDMPs into the shared repository (we will be using ARGOS/Zenodo so presumably it will link).</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> The pilot plans to engage with local stakeholders to develop maDMP templates tailored to local infrastructure and funding body requirements. This development will occur within the ARGOS platform.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u></p>

	<p>The approach to archiving maDMPs and linking them to publications and other research outputs will be determined by the working group during the project.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u></p> <p>The co-definition of FAIR metrics with stakeholders will be addressed by the working group under the guidance of project partners.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u></p> <p>Currently, the assessment of the FAIRness of deposited digital objects (DOs) and repositories is managed locally within project partners and does not occur at scale or strategically. The pilot plans to implement a protocol/system for this, based on the tools provided via the OSTrails project.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u></p> <p>At present, DMP evaluation is conducted locally by each institution based on funder requirements and general best practices. There is no joint evaluation process.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u></p> <p>Monitoring and reporting take place via cRIS systems, repository statistics, and the National Open Access Monitor.</p>
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Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 7 maDMP templates, incl. funders - 60 FAIR assessed digital objects - 40% of researchers across the 5 Irish TUs engaged
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Pilot activities	Timeline
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - develop maDMP templates. - organise 5 webinars (1 per institution) for researchers to present ARGOS, highlighting interoperability of published DMPs with other systems, and promote the creation and publication of DMPs in line with both institutional and funder requirements. - call for min 2 x research groups to trial and co-develop the local instances and templates, test FAIR assessment tool. - run 5 x training workshops (1 per institution) 	<p>the 9 funded months</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - investigate and where possible implement the FAIR assessment tool at repository level(s)/ - investigate and where possible develop interoperability between cRIS system (PURE) and ARGOS 	
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4.10. N-9: Portuguese National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-9: Portuguese National Pilot
Key organisations	University of Minho (UMinho) leads the pilot, bringing significant experience in research data management and open science initiatives. The Foundation for Science and Technology (FCT) is the national public agency supporting research in science, technology, and innovation across various knowledge domains.
Objectives	<p>The Portuguese national pilot aims to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop maDMP models. Configure and relate these models with national CRIS initiatives, institutional research portals, and repositories. Foster interoperability with the OpenAIRE Research Graph. Co-define metrics and criteria for evaluating DMPs in collaboration with FCT. Evaluate the FAIRness of Digital Objects (DOs) in the research data repositories of both partners.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<p>The Open Science policy at UMinho is under approval, which includes specific guidelines regarding Research Data Management (RDM).</p> <p>Since 2014, FCT has been issuing recommendations to comply with RDM best practices. A formal RDM policy aligned with FAIR principles is expected to come into force soon. FCT is enhancing infrastructures and services to ensure compliance with the policy and with RDM best practices.</p>
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Both organisations aim to strengthen FAIR principles by offering RDM services contributing to FAIR data practices. This includes the development of maDMP templates, the assessment of the FAIRness of digital objects deposited in both data repositories and ensuring that these principles are embedded within their policies.

Involvement in EOSC	<p>UMinho: Actively involved in EU projects such as EOSC-Beyond and EOSC-Future, and is member of the OpenAIRE AMKE, contributing to the development of key EOSC core components. FCT: Member of the EOSC Association with national representatives in EOSC's Steering Board. Actively participates in several Open Science projects, including EOSC-Synergy.</p>
Affiliation with National Funders	<p>The pilot includes FCT, the primary national funder.</p>
Description of Activities	<p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u> UMinho: Needs FAIR assessment for digital objects in the data repository (Dataverse) and improvements in maDMP models and integration with CRIS initiatives. FCT: Requires enhancements in the Polen Research Data Repository (based on Dataverse) for FAIR assessments, improvements in the maDMP model, and better integration of the DMP Service (based on Argos) with national CRIS initiative.</p> <p><u>Required Components for End-to-End Solutions:</u> Alignment with WP1 and WP2 developments.</p> <p><u>Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements:</u> Both institutions aim to ensure FAIRness of research outputs and actionability of DMPs.</p> <p><u>Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs:</u> UMinho and FCT are aware of tools like F-UJI but have not implemented them regularly in their workflows. Both lack experience in DMP assessment.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:</u> Both institutions will test and evaluate the data repository (Dataverse) and DMP tools (openDMP and Argos instances).</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs:</u> UMinho: Data repository compatible with OpenAIRE guidelines, and metadata harvested by OpenAIRE. FCT: Plans to implement a research portal using data harvested by OpenAIRE Graph.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> Development of two maDMP templates, one for each organisation, within the OSTrails pilot.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> Both institutions plan to archive maDMPs in their respective repositories.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> Engagement of researchers and funder officers to promote the definition and use of FAIR metrics.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u> Both institutions have curation workflows for metadata quality but need new procedures for FAIR assessments.</p>

	<p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u> No established criteria yet; to be developed and validated through the pilot.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u> UMinho: Lacks monitoring and reporting procedures. FCT: Implementing a system to verify compliance with Open Science requirements, focusing initially on open access to publications and later on RDM requirements.</p>
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 maDMP templates, incl. funder; 400 researchers engaged; 1600 FAIR assessed digital objects.

Pilot activities	Timeline
Develop maDMP templates in line with WP1 and WP2 activities (KPI: 2 maDMP templates)	
Initial Design Phase	Month 18-21
Testing and Validation	Month 21-24
Finalise Templates	Month 24
Organise webinars and workshops, targeted to UMinho and FCT beneficiaries, to present the DMP tools (openDMP and Argos) and to highlight the interoperability of published DMPs with other systems, promoting the creation of DMPs in line with both institutional and funder requirements (KPI: engage 400 researchers to prepare a DMP)	
Planning and Initial Outreach	Month 18-21
First Round of Webinars and Workshops (ca 150 researchers)	Month 21-24
Continued Engagement (ca 150 researchers)	Month 24-30
Final Engagement (ca 100 researchers)	Month 30-36
Implement the FAIR assessment tool in both repositories (in line with WP2 activities) and assess the FAIRness of deposited digital objects (KPI: 1600 FAIR assessed digital objects).	
Initial Integration	Month 18-21
Start FAIR Assessments (ca 400 Digital Objects)	Month 21-24
Scale-Up of FAIR Assessments (600 Digital Object)	Month 24-30
Full Implementation (600 Digital Objects)	Month 30-36

4.11. N-10: French National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-10: French National Pilot
Key organisations	INRIA is the French national research institute for digital science and technology, focusing on digital sciences and leading open science activities (e.g., Software Heritage initiative, the development of the French OS monitor). It is part of the French Recherche Data Gouv ecosystem and contributes to defining conditions for a better integration of software in data management plans and linking these to relevant publications citing software and data.
Objectives	This pilot expects to agree in the pilot on a metadata model for describing source code and software in DMPs when they have been used in relation to the datasets described in the DMPs (for creation, transformation or visualisation). A second expected outcome is an interoperability framework allowing software description in repositories (typically HAL) to automatically feed DMPs. Both could be implemented in the French DMP tool (DMP Opidor) and benefit the whole community.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	INRIA has established a dedicated unit with four people for RDM, supporting researchers in DMP writing and data/software sharing. They have pioneered OS software infrastructure and are deeply involved in improving DMP software integration.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Inria is committed to FAIR principles, focusing on the integration of software into DMPs and the archiving of maDMPs in the French national repository HAL. They are working closely with the French Recherche Data Gouv ecosystem to achieve this.
Involvement in EOSC	Inria is the EOSC mandated member for France and participates in several EOSC projects, including FAIRCORE4EOSC, FAIRIMPACT, and GRASP OS.
Affiliation with National Funders	The national pilot is not directly affiliated with national funders.
Description of Activities	<p>The French national pilot will</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improve DMP software integration. • Assess the conditions to allow the archiving maDMPs in the French national repository HAL. • Develop a metadata model for describing source code and software in DMPs. • Establish an interoperability framework for software description in repositories. <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u></p>

	<p>FAIR assessment is in early development stages in France.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> Inria plans to develop maDMP templates that address local infrastructure and funding body requirements.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> Currently, the vast majority of DMPs at Inria are not archived or linked to publications and other research outputs.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> The organisation plans to engage stakeholders to co-define FAIR metrics</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u> Inria does not currently assess the FAIRness of deposited digital objects and repositories. The research data unit supports researchers who wish to share data in a FAIR manner.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u> No formal criteria have been set to evaluate DMPs. The research data unit only offers support in writing DMPs in the FAIRest way possible.</p>
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 maDMP templates (for INRIA and for CS French Community); 2000 researchers engaged.

Pilot activities	Timeline
agree upon a template for software description in DMPs	August 2024
validate a mapping between a metadata model (codemeta) and the DMP model described above	End of 2024
develop maDMP templates in line with WP1 and WP2 activities (KPI: 2 maDMP templates), define how maDMP can be automatically fed (regarding source code and software components)	2025
work on archiving maDMPs in the French repository HAL	2026
Organise webinars and workshops to present software description and to highlight the interoperability of published DMPs with other systems	now - end of the project

4.12. N-11: Finnish National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-11: Finnish National Pilot
Key organisations	CSC - IT Centre for Science leads the national pilot in Finland. As a non-profit state enterprise with a special mandate, CSC strives to provide holistic solutions, serving the Finnish research community from planning to reporting and assessment. CSC coordinates the DMP Consortium, develops the FAIR data services and the national CRIS system, and hosts the funding application management tool of the prime funder, Academy of Finland. Both the national DMP Consortium and the Finnish National Open Science Coordination will be highly involved, assuring an even higher impact on the whole Finnish research community.
Objectives	<p>Pilot focus will be on data interoperability rather than on building specific solutions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop a national machine-actionable DMP (maDMP) template tailored for Finnish funders and local infrastructure. • Align the maDMP template with EU DMP standards (e.g., ERC, Horizon, Science Europe) and RDA standards. • Collect use cases to digitalize the research data management process. • Enhance data interoperability and serve researchers, research institutes, and research funders more effectively. • Facilitate the use of maDMPs across 60 organisations in Finland.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	CSC has a RDM policy.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	CSC is actively involved in strengthening FAIR principles through its services and various national and international development projects. The national pilot is fundamentally based on the FAIR principles and has been presented in the national roadshow of the FAIR-IMPACT National Roadshow in Finland.
Involvement in EOSC	CSC is a member of the EOSC Association and striving actively to forward the EOSC initiative in Finland as well as participating in numerous EOSC projects.

Affiliation with National Funders	<p>The pilot is affiliated with the Research Council of Finland, with plans to increase involvement from other funders, endorsing the benefits of the maDMPs for the funders.</p>
Description of Activities	<p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u> Current DMPs are not machine-actionable. There is a need for a national template that fully facilitates the potential of maDMPs.</p> <p><u>Required Components for End-to-End Solutions:</u> Contributions to the development of DMP tools, particularly in WP4, are beneficial. Although the focus in the pilot is to promote interoperability rather than technical solutions, the pilot collects use cases for maDMPs and works closely with the development of DMPTuuli, observing also the development of other DMP tools.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:</u> The pilot includes testing of DMPTuuli for further development of machine actionability for the identified use cases, and potentially other tools.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs:</u> The pilot observes developments related to OpenAIRE Graph and other SKGs.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> Developing the maDMP national template is a core focus of the OSTrails FI National Pilot.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> Public DMPs are distributed via DMPTuuli. Other DMPs are archived within research organisations according to their policies. The use and development of common repositories will be observed in the pilot.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> Co-definition of FAIR metrics is not included in the selected use cases of the pilot, but knowledge dissemination will occur.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u> The use of digital objects (DOs) and persistent identifiers (PIDs) is encouraged and promoted as linkages between systems to promote active machine actionability. Commonly used and other potential DOs and repositories will be examined in the pilot.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u> DMP evaluation criteria will be potentially assessed as part of the pilot.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u> The pilot communicates on the possibilities of plausible development paths of maDMPs to be integrated with the national monitoring and funders reporting systems development groups. However, the development and</p>

	implementation of any extensions are out of the focus of this national pilot.														
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	1 maDMP template; 60 Institutions and their researchers engaged.														
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pilot activities</th> <th>Timeline</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td colspan="2"> <p>The pilot has begun in March 2024, and the maDMP development is ongoing. The pilot has had national kick-off in March 2024, online webinars in April, May and June. The next one-day workshop will be held in September 2024.</p> <p>Timeline is the 34 months during which further activities are conducted to reach the national maDMP template gathering national needs from WP4 with communications supported by WP5, contributing to WP1 and WP2, and implementing the OSTrails Commons for the national maDMP template.</p> </td> </tr> <tr> <td>Raise awareness of the maDMP and examine the purpose for efficiency of research ecosystem</td> <td>Feb 2024 - Dec 2024</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Identify local infrastructure gaps</td> <td>Mar 2024 - Dec 2024</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Investigate and document components for end-to-end solutions and define the national maDMP template</td> <td>Sep 2024 - May 2025</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Identify characteristics of local community requirements to support integration of appropriate DMP tools, FAIR metrics and quality assessment of DMPs</td> <td>Jan 2025 - Dec 2026</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Test and evaluate tools and OSTrails Commons and provide feedback for further development</td> <td>June 2025 - Jan 2027</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pilot activities	Timeline	<p>The pilot has begun in March 2024, and the maDMP development is ongoing. The pilot has had national kick-off in March 2024, online webinars in April, May and June. The next one-day workshop will be held in September 2024.</p> <p>Timeline is the 34 months during which further activities are conducted to reach the national maDMP template gathering national needs from WP4 with communications supported by WP5, contributing to WP1 and WP2, and implementing the OSTrails Commons for the national maDMP template.</p>		Raise awareness of the maDMP and examine the purpose for efficiency of research ecosystem	Feb 2024 - Dec 2024	Identify local infrastructure gaps	Mar 2024 - Dec 2024	Investigate and document components for end-to-end solutions and define the national maDMP template	Sep 2024 - May 2025	Identify characteristics of local community requirements to support integration of appropriate DMP tools, FAIR metrics and quality assessment of DMPs	Jan 2025 - Dec 2026	Test and evaluate tools and OSTrails Commons and provide feedback for further development	June 2025 - Jan 2027
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4.13. N-12: German National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-12: German National Pilot
Key organisations	<p>The German pilot is led by RWTH Aachen University Library, with support by ULB Darmstadt and ZBMed. The National Research Data Infrastructure (NFDI) is involved via its base service consortium. NFDI4Chem and NFDI4Ing respectively provide the Chemistry and Engineering domain applications.</p> <p>NFDIs have formed in Germany to coordinate national RDM developments and build an open and FAIR infrastructure research adhering to the Berlin Declaration on NFDI Cross-</p>

	<p>Cutting Topics. NFDI 4Chem and NFDI4Ing participate in RDA to co-define DMP discipline specific criteria. For years, RWTH Aachen University has been involved in various networks such as TU9 - the association of the nine largest technical universities in Germany. TU9 stands for future-oriented research in engineering and natural sciences. Furthermore, RWTH participates in the further development of RDMO and is also active internationally in RDA working groups.</p>
Objectives	<p>The key focus of the German pilot is to integrate the widely used national DMP tool "Research Data Management Organizer (RDMO)" with electronic lab notebooks/repositories, specifically "Chemotion" and "eLabFTW". The integration aims to carry over considerations documented in data management plans to tools used in other stages of a project, enhancing interoperability and data sharing.</p>
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<p>RWTH has a policy, but it varies for the other organisations in Germany.</p>
Commitment to FAIR Principles	<p>NFDI aims to strengthen FAIR principles by fostering interoperability and integration while offering centralised infrastructure.</p>
Involvement in EOSC	<p>The German pilot is connected to EOSC via involvement of NFDI.</p>
Affiliation with National Funders	<p>The German pilot is connected to national funders via involvement of NFDI.</p>
Description of Activities	<p>Integration between RDMO and two subject-specific tools (Chemotion, eLabFTW), experience on such integrations in general, and possibly input for automated assessment of DMPs.</p> <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u></p> <p>While RDMO provides an API, there are few integrations with other tools yet. This pilot focuses on integrating RDMO with electronic lab notebooks (Chemotion, eLabFTW).</p> <p><u>Required Components for End-to-End Solutions:</u></p> <p>Implementation of integration between RDMO and electronic lab notebooks via APIs. A general framework for establishing integrations with other tools will be explored.</p> <p><u>Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements:</u></p>

	<p>Need to integrate DMPs with tools where the real work happens, specifically electronic lab notebooks.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:</u> Will be discussed with stakeholders as part of the project and within the NFDI common infrastructure.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs:</u> RWTH institutional repositories already deliver to OpenAIRE. No clear connection with RDMO yet but the general idea of integrating the DMP tool with other tools via SKGs has its appeal.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates:</u> Since June 2024 the project DMP4NFDI has been started. It is currently in the initialisation phase of a base service for the national research data infrastructure (NFDI). The project has three partners: RWTH, TU Darmstadt and ZBmed (Information Centre for Life Sciences) and addresses three aspects: hosting, training & support, and template management. RWTH Aachen is responsible for the latter part. The goal is to make it easier for researchers from different subjects to arrive at suitable machine actionable data management plan templates by combining questionnaires, reusing answer options and means to add specific helping texts while at the same time keeping the foundational and encompassing domain model concise. The latter part is essential in regard to the efforts tackled by OSTrails. With a well-maintained core, it is much easier to connect the RDMO tool to other tools, map it to other DMP tools and thus address the international interoperability targeted in OSTrails.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> No dedicated approach yet. DMPs could be archived/published in institutional repositories but are preferably referred to within the RDMO tool as living objects during project runtime.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> Suitable FAIR metrics will arise depending on the integration with tools.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems:</u> Some user groups already use DMPs to monitor their projects/outcomes.</p>
<p>Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)</p>	<p>2 maDMP templates; 2 communities: NFDI4Chem & NFDI4Ing; 30 FAIR assessed digital objects.</p>

Pilot activities	Timeline
<p>Summer 2024 - Summer 2025</p> <p>Within the DMP4NFDI project we are currently rolling out the base service RDMO (the German DMP tool) to various subject-specific research fields. This process is intended to run for one year and includes the design of a DMP template management framework to alleviate the burden of designing subject-specific and machine-actional DMP templates.</p> <p>During the design of the management framework, we watch out to the outcomes of the WP 1 to 3 of OSTrails in order to align our work with the intended international standards. It is thus essential that we kept in the loop of the developments happening there.</p> <p>In addition, we approach a first integration effort by considering a connection between RDMO and the Coscine research data management platform at RWTH Aachen University. By means of API calls and possibly SKGs a connection between these software tools is to be established. This integration effort ist supposed to pave the way for the integration efforts to be targeted within the OSTrails project. We are anticipating a follow-up funding phase starting next year to continue establishing the base service within NFDI by applying the framework and supporting more disciplines and communities.</p> <p>Preliminary timeline of actions within OSTrails (partially depending on advancements and findings in DMP4NFDI project):</p>	
<p>Review of Interoperability Framework, OSTrails Software and Services and OSTrails Commons Specification. Checking for integration means via SKGs.</p>	<p>08-2025 - 11-2025</p>
<p>Aligning the subject-specific DMP templates for NFDI4Ing and NFDI4CHEM with OSTrails means. Proof of concept for interoperability.</p>	<p>12-2025 - 02-2026</p>
<p>Implementing integration with first electronic lab book application (either Chemotion or eLabFTW based on current situation then) including try out phase within both application partners NFDI4Ing and NFDI4CHEM but also open to any other subject using that electronic lab book software.</p>	<p>03-2026 - 05-2026</p>
<p>Implementing the integration with the second electronic lab book application, massively building on the previous experience thus expecting much less workload.</p>	<p>06-2026 - 07-2026</p>

4.14. N-13: Spanish National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-13: Spanish National Pilot
Key organisations	<p>The Foundation for Science and Technology (FECYT) is the main agency for promoting scientific culture and Open Science in Spain. It is a public institution under the Ministry for Science, Innovation and Universities that implements OS public policies through strengthening digital infrastructures like open access repositories, CRIS systems and publication services.</p> <p>FECYT deploys two main policy tools: it is both a funding agency for OS digital infrastructures and a quality certification agency at the national level.</p> <p>Certification services for open access repositories are based on metadata quality and on policies, interoperability, statistics and visibility quality.</p> <p>RECOLECTA (recolecta.fecyt.es) is the national harvester for open access repositories in Spain, focused on facilitating metadata interoperability at the national level and providing with access, visibility and impact to scientific research outputs. It provides the following services to the national community of open access repositories: metadata validation; metadata enrichment; quality assessment, harvesting; usage statistics; and a search engine.</p>
Objectives	<p>The main objective of this pilot is to enhance the quality, standardisation, and evaluation processes of DMPs within the Spanish research community. To achieve this, several concrete objectives are listed below:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create a standardised template for DMPs for the repository community following the structure and content proposed by ARGOS. ● Validate the quality of the DMPs metadata through RECOLECTA validation service. ● Link DMPs with their associated key research artefacts. ● Enrich DMP metadata with their missing information. ● Provide DMP with visibility and usage metrics.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analyze, together with the funding agency, the DMP minimum quality criteria to be applied in the assessment process. Develop a natural language processing (NLP) based tool for funders to analyse DMP quality content.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<p>Entities receiving project funding from the Spanish State Research Agency (AEI) must ensure that research results, including publications, data, codes, and methodologies, are available in open access and deposited in repositories according to Article 37 of Law 14/2011 and to Article 12 of the Universities Spanish Organic Law 2/2023. These results must adhere to FAIR principles to facilitate validation and reusability. In addition, the National Open Science Strategy (ENCA) calls for research data management to follow FAIR principles and fosters open science practices at public R&D funding.</p> <p>The implementation status of RDM policies has not been measured yet. The OSTrails national pilot will largely contribute to it.</p>
Commitment to FAIR Principles	<p>FECYT aims to strengthen the implementation of FAIR principles in DMPs through metadata validation services, repository assessment open calls, and metadata enrichment services.</p>
Involvement in EOSC	<p>FECYT represents Spain at the EOSC Steering Board, participated in EOSC Future, and belongs to several OS initiatives that will be part of the EOSC federated nodes like OPERAS ESFRI and OpenAIRE AMKE.</p>
Affiliation with National Funders	<p>The main R&D funder in Spain in the National Research Agency (AEI). It is a public entity that depends on the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. Both AEI and FECYT operate under the same organisational structure, though they are separate institutions. Besides, FECYT is also an R&D funder for OS digital infrastructures: open access repositories, CRIS systems and publication services.</p>
Description of Activities	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Development and promotion of DMP templates: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Create and distribute standardised templates for DMPs based on the ARGOS structure, tailored to the needs of the Spanish research community.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Develop guidelines and resources to help researchers on using these templates. ○ Develop guidelines and resources to help repository managers with DMP long term preservation. <p>2. Metadata quality:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Provide guidance to researchers and repositories to improve their metadata quality, ensuring alignment with FAIR principles. ○ Ensure standardised metadata across repositories. ○ Implement a metadata enrichment service for DMPs. ○ Implement a metadata linking mechanism for DMPs and its key research artefacts. <p>3. Content quality</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Work closely with the Spanish State Research Agency (AEI) to define quality criteria for evaluating DMPs, ensuring these criteria align with both national and international standards. ○ Develop guidelines and resources to help researchers meet these criteria. ○ Design and implement an automated analysis system using NLP to evaluate DMPs, focusing on identifying key quality indicators. <p>4. Training activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conduct training sessions to raise awareness about the importance of DMPs FAIRness among researchers and research performing institutions. ○ Conduct training sessions to raise awareness about the importance of DMPs content quality among researchers and research performing institutions. ○ Develop training resources to support the implementation of these practices. <p>Through these activities, FECYT aims to ensure that research data management practices in Spain align with international standards and contribute to the National Strategy for Open Science (ENCA).</p> <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps:</u> Not all open access repositories provide DMP archiving services. Besides, FAIRness of DMPs is not a technical requirement from the main national research funder.</p>
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Moreover, the national funding agency (AEI) lacks the capability to machine-read and analyse DMPs content. This national pilot will facilitate those repositories to be able to upload DMP files whose content can be automatically analysed by any funder.

Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements:

The national pilot will work on two ends. First, on strengthening our technical services through FAIRness provision and validation services. Second, on facilitating the work of the AEI in DMP quality assessment.

Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs:

RECOLECTA applies metadata validation protocols to the national repositories. This validation is based on Dublin Core (oai_dc) and Data Cite (oai_oaire) metadata schema and follows the Guidelines for Institutional Repositories⁷.

DMP are validated at the metadata level, following Dublin Core and Data Cite metadata schemes. No content quality validation has been designed yet for any research output at RECOLECTA level, nor for DMP.

The national pilot will develop a natural language processing-based tool for DMP content quality assessment.

Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services:

FECYT will use its already existing RECOLECTA metadata certification and enrichment services to guarantee DMP FAIRness.

FECYT will develop a new certification service for DMP content quality.

Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs:

FECYT is a data provider for OpenAIRE and serves as the central node for the national repositories' community.

Development of maDMP Templates:

FECYT will coordinate the technical work with the main national research funder (AEI) and the national repository community. The content of the template will be based on ARGO's proposal.

⁷ <https://recolecta.fecyt.es/documentacion/guia-para-la-evaluacion-de-repositorios-institucionales-de-investigacion>

	<p><u>Archiving of maDMPs:</u> Through persistent identifiers managed by repositories and standardised metadata.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics:</u> Through a co-creation process with the repository’s community and the above-mentioned funding agency.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories:</u> Through the metadata validation service. The RECOLECTA metadata validator will include an extension that will allow discriminating the DMPs from the rest of the harvested records.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria:</u> To be discussed during the project. FECYT will consult with the national main funder regarding DMP content quality criteria.</p> <p><u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder’s Reporting Systems:</u> These services will be developed in close collaboration with both the main research funding agency (AEI) and the national repositories community.</p>										
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	1 maDMP template; 1500 FAIR assessed digital objects.										
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4.15. N-14: Czech National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-14: Czech National Pilot
Key organisations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESNET: The national academic networks provider responsible for deploying the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) in the Czech Republic. CESNET's role in the pilot includes providing infrastructure for setting up the archiving of machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and deploying FAIR Evaluator. • Czech Technical University (CTU): Working alongside CESNET, CTU's focus is on assessing the FAIRness

	<p>(Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of its digital objects in DSpace.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Library of Technology (NTK): Collaborating with CTU to develop maDMP templates and assessment metrics. • Czech Science Foundation & Technology Agency of Czech Republic: The major national funders, both agreed to co-define DMP evaluation criteria and discuss how to implement policies on FAIR data.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop maDMP templates for NTK, including metrics within the template to assess DMPs against FAIRness of their described artefacts. • Assess FAIRness of CTU digital objects. • Deploy the DMP Evaluator Tool. • Co-define DMP evaluation criteria with national funders: Czech Science Foundation and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESNET: Currently does not have a specific RDM policy related to the pilot but is committed to implementing and promoting FAIR solutions. • NTK: NTK has been implementing European standards in the Czech research environment and actively cooperating with key actors supporting R&I, especially in the field of Open Science. • Local Funders (Czech Science Foundation & Technology Agency of Czech Republic): Both organisations are in the process of developing policies that emphasise the importance of FAIR data. • CTU: Has ongoing processes to establish robust RDM policies.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CESNET: Just a provider but committed to providing and promoting FAIR solutions. • NTK: Actively promotes FAIR principles through tutorials, conferences, and other initiatives. • Local Funders: Both major funders are committed to installing policies that strengthen FAIR principles. • CTU: At an early stage of awareness and implementation but is actively working on promoting the importance of FAIR principles.
Involvement in EOSC	<p>Apart from the pilots, there is currently a project of "EOSC implementation in the Czech Republic" – building of the National Repository Platform, where CTU is also involved.</p>
Affiliation with National Funders	<p>Two major Czech funders are partners in the pilot.</p>

Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CESNET: Infrastructure provider. ● NTK: Acting as a consensus maker at the national level. ● Local Funders: Improving policies and support for DMP and FAIR evaluation. ● CTU: Improving the FAIRness of digital objects in DSpace. <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: Identified the need for maDMP templates and assessment metrics. ● Local Funders: Recognized weak and vague policies on FAIR data and data management planning. ● CTU: Focused on evaluating the FAIRness of digital objects. <p><u>Required Components for End-to-End Solutions</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● CESNET: Hosting a DMP evaluation service. ● NTK: Developing DMP evaluation rubrics and assessment metrics. ● Local Funders: Developing DMP evaluation rubrics and assessment metrics. ● CTU: Implementing testing services. <p><u>Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: Needs methods, tools, and guidance for effective implementation. ● Local Funders: Requires policies and tools to support FAIR principles. ● CTU: Requires easy-to-use solutions for researchers. <p><u>Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: No prior experience with assessment methods. ● Local Funders: Currently, assessments are administrative rather than content based. ● CTU: Early adoption and testing of the Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW). <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: Plans to define and test methods as part of the pilot. ● Local Funders: No commitment yet. ● CTU: Committed to testing and evaluation within the pilot. <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs</u></p> <p>NTK: Interested in potential interactions.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: Plans to define maDMP templates. ● Local Funders: May develop templates depending on the internal stage of FAIR evaluation. <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs</u></p> <p>CESNET: Infrastructure support for maDMP archiving.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● NTK: Through meetings and workshops.
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Funders: Through meetings and workshops. <u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories</u> CTU: Currently none, but a goal of the pilot. <u>DMP Evaluation Criteria</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Funders: Currently administrative, not content based. CTU: Awaiting requirements from funders. <u>Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Local Funders: Depends on the current status and future developments. CTU: Uses an internal system for scientific output assessment.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	2 ma-DMP templates; 100 FAIR assessed digital objects; 3 Universities adopting OSTrails results.

Pilot activities	Timeline
maDMP templates for NTK + assessment metrics	M18-M30
analysis done	M19
implementation + 1st metrics done (2 templates)	M23
evaluation performed	M27
2nd version of metrics + feedback from evaluation	M30
DMP evaluator tool deployment	M29
co-definition of evaluation criteria with national funders	duration: M18-M26
1st version of evaluation criteria gathered	M22
criteria validated and finalised	M26
assessment of FAIRness of CTU digital objects	M28-36
test set of DOs collected	M29
measurements collected	M33
results processed and evaluated	M36

4.16. N-15: Swedish National Pilot: State of Play and Implementation Plan

Pilot Number & Title	N-15: Swedish National Pilot
Key organisations	The Swedish National Data Service - SND is a national infrastructure for open access to research data supporting the accessibility, preservation, and reuse of research data and related materials. SND has 38 universities and public research institutes as members in its network. The SND leads the pilot, with ongoing discussions about participation with Chalmers Technical University. Final confirmation of additional partners is pending.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop ma-template for DMPs based on the SND Checklist for DMPs, embedding FAIR metrics within the template to assess DMPs against FAIRness of their described artefacts. • Align with DORIS and explore links with local and national CRIS systems - SweCRIS and interoperate with the OpenAIRE Graph. • Assess FAIRness of SND DORIS digital objects. • Deploy DMP Evaluator Tool at SND.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	SND has well-established RDM policies that guide their operations. These policies are accessible on ZENODO at https://zenodo.org/records/6477109 and https://zenodo.org/records/6477041
Commitment to FAIR Principles	SND has a long-term commitment to FAIR and continually work with increasing the FAIR score of data published through SND.
Involvement in EOSC	Although the formal mission of EOSC establishment in Sweden lies with the Swedish Research Council, SND are active in various national projects (e.g. researchdata.se) and international projects (e.g. ATRIUM, Skills4EOSC). SND is also has representatives in two of the EOSC Task Forces.
Affiliation with National Funders	SND is funded by the Swedish Research Council
Description of Activities	The Swedish National Pilot aims to enhance the interoperability between SND's technical systems for data publication and the local Data Management Plan (DMP) and Current Research Information Systems (CRIS) at universities. The primary goal is to increase the FAIRness (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) of published data while reducing the workload on researchers during the data publishing process. This will be achieved by implementing machine-actionable DMPs (ma-

	<p>DMPs). Additionally, the pilot will deploy a FAIR evaluation tool to assess the FAIR score of published objects.</p> <p><u>Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps</u></p> <p>Sweden's e-infrastructure for research is fragmented, with minimal interoperability between organisations. While cooperation exists, it is mostly limited to knowledge exchange rather than technical implementation. SND has initiated a collaborative project called researchdata.se, involving eight other national research infrastructures, to address this fragmentation and promote common standards and procedures.</p> <p><u>Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements</u></p> <p>At present, no formal procedures exist to evaluate DMPs, which limits their machine-actionability. The data published through SND undergoes rigorous quality assurance, ensuring a high FAIR score. Organisations participating in the SND network depend on SND for high-quality data and metadata.</p> <p><u>Experience with Assessment Methods for Outputs and DMPs</u></p> <p>SND performs quality assurance on all published data and metadata. The organisation has nearly 50 years of experience in RDM activities.</p> <p><u>Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services</u></p> <p>The pilot plans to evaluate a FAIR evaluation tool and explore how Semantic Knowledge Graphs (SKGs) can enhance interoperability across platforms.</p> <p><u>Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or Other SKGs</u></p> <p>This is under consideration, with plans to assess how SKGs can be used to improve interoperability in the Swedish context.</p> <p><u>Development of maDMP Templates</u></p> <p>Work on developing maDMP templates has already started, particularly with Chalmers Technical University, aiming to enhance machine-actionability in their systems. Discussions are also ongoing with the University of Gothenburg, which plans to establish a new DMP tool featuring a ma-DMP template based on the SND Checklist for Data Management Plans.</p> <p><u>Archiving of maDMPs</u></p> <p>Data Management Plans are archived at local universities along with other research project outputs. While archiving is typically a separate process from data publication, local initiatives are underway to streamline this process.</p> <p><u>Co-definition of FAIR Metrics</u></p> <p>This is still undecided but is expected to be part of the pilot's objectives.</p> <p><u>Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories</u></p> <p>SND annually evaluates the FAIRness score of published data using the F-UJI tool. Based on these evaluations, SND makes</p>
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	<p>adjustments to its systems or metadata profiles as necessary. As part of the pilot, SND also plans to test and deploy a FAIR evaluation tool locally.</p> <p><u>DMP Evaluation Criteria</u></p> <p>Currently, there are no national criteria for DMP evaluation, except for a general requirement that projects should have a DMP. Some universities offer support and light evaluation for DMPs, but there is no standardised approach.</p>						
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	1 maDMP template; 2 Universities and their researchers engaged; 1000 FAIR assessed digital objects.						
<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Pilot activities</th> <th>Timeline</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>maDMP template, adaptation and evaluation</td> <td>March 2025 - March 2026</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Assessment of digital objects, including deployment of assessment tool:</td> <td>March 2025 - December 2025</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>		Pilot activities	Timeline	maDMP template, adaptation and evaluation	March 2025 - March 2026	Assessment of digital objects, including deployment of assessment tool:	March 2025 - December 2025
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5. Thematic Pilots

5.1. Overview / Background

The thematic pilots within the OSTrails project are performed by research infrastructures representing all **five ESFRI Science Clusters**. These thematic pilots are a critical component of the overall initiative, designed to validate and demonstrate the effectiveness of the methodologies, tools, and frameworks developed in the project. They are strategically chosen to represent a diverse range of scientific domains and organisational contexts, each with unique challenges and requirements for Research Data Management (RDM) and FAIR principles implementation.

The thematic pilots are integral to achieving the overarching goals of OSTrails by serving as real-world testbeds where theoretical concepts and developed tools can be applied, refined, and validated. Each pilot is embedded in its respective community, ensuring that the solutions developed are not only technically sound but also relevant and adoptable by the target users. The pilots cover a wide spectrum of scientific disciplines, from life sciences and environmental research to astronomy and social sciences, reflecting the interdisciplinary nature of the OSTrails project.

The pilots' involvement with the broader OSTrails framework is multifaceted. They are not only recipients of the project's outputs but also active contributors to the design and development processes through participation of research communities in the WP1, WP2 and WP3. Also, the list of auxiliary services that will support the OSTrails Commons was initially provided by the research communities. By using the instrument of thematic

pilots, OSTrails ensures that the tools and methodologies are aligned with the actual needs of the scientific communities they are designed to serve. In addition to the involvement of the research communities in the design and development processes, this bidirectional relationship allows for continuous testing, feedback and iterative improvement, which is essential for the project's success.

5.2. Integration with OSTrails Framework

The integration of thematic pilots with the OSTrails framework occurs through several key mechanisms:

1. **Development of Machine-Actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs):** Many of the pilots focus on transforming traditional, static Data Management Plans (DMPs) into dynamic, machine-actionable versions. These maDMPs are central to the OSTrails objective of creating an interconnected ecosystem where data management is automated, interoperable, and compliant with FAIR principles, and community standards accessed in FAIRsharing. For instance, pilots like PaNOSC and ENVRI/JERICO are actively working on enhancing DMP templates to support this transition, aligning closely with the goals of WP1 and WP2.
2. **Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs):** The pilots are also heavily involved in the development and integration of Scientific Knowledge Graphs, which serve as the backbone for data interoperability and accessibility within the OSTrails framework. Pilots such as SSHOC/CLARIN are focused on extending existing data catalogues into SKGs, thereby enhancing their ability to interlink various research outputs and support comprehensive FAIR assessments; while FAIRsharing provides relationships among standards and between standards and databases, across all science clusters. This work is crucial for WP3, which deals with creating and refining FAIR metrics and assessment tools.
3. **FAIR Assessment Tools:** A key aspect of many pilots is the development and implementation of FAIR assessment tools tailored to specific scientific domains. These tools are designed to go beyond generic assessments and address the unique needs of different communities. For example, the ESCAPE/ObsParis pilot is working on adapting FAIR assessment criteria to the requirements of the astronomy community, thereby contributing to the project's broader aim of creating customizable, community-specific solutions. The FAIRsharing pilot will provide FAIR assessment and assistance tools with a look-up service to verify the standards declared or necessary.
4. **Interoperability and Standardization:** The pilots play a role in testing and implementing the interoperability standards developed within OSTrails. By participating in initiatives like EOSC, the pilots help ensure that the tools and methodologies are compatible with existing infrastructures and can be seamlessly integrated into the broader EOSC ecosystem. This alignment is critical for the long-term sustainability and scalability of the OSTrails solutions.

5. **Feedback and Iterative Improvement:** The pilots provide continuous feedback to the OSTrails development teams, helping to refine the tools and ensure they meet the needs of the end-users. This iterative process is important for ensuring that the solutions developed are not only technically robust but also practically applicable in real-world research environments.

In summary, together with the national pilots, thematic pilots provide the necessary link between theory and practice. Through their involvement, OSTrails ensures that its solutions are not only innovative but also practical and adoptable by the broader scientific community. The successful integration of these pilots into the OSTrails framework will be a significant step towards realising the project's vision of a fully interconnected, FAIR-compliant research data management ecosystem.

The thematic pilots are the following one:

- **T1 - FAIRsharing for ESFRI Science Clusters.** - Focuses on enhancing FAIRsharing as a collaborative resource for community standards, databases, and policies. The pilot aims to integrate FAIRsharing content with OSTrails components for improved interoperability across science clusters.
- **T2 - PaNOSC / ESRF, SOLEIL, ILL.**- Works on automating the generation of machine-actionable DMPs (maDMPs) within the Photon and Neutron communities. The pilot will contribute to the transformation of DMPs into dynamic resources aligned with FAIR principles.
- **T3 - ENVRI / JERICO.** - Extends the JERICO e-infrastructure by integrating DMPs and digital objects. It focuses on developing an interoperable schema for SKGs and enhancing data monitoring and reporting within marine research.
- **T5 - SSHOC/CESSDA.** - Aims to improve the interoperability and FAIRness of social science datasets by adapting the CESSDA Vocabulary Service and European Language Social Science Thesaurus to the DMP Interoperability Framework. The pilot will also integrate FAIR assessment tools into CESSDA services.
- **T6 - SSHOC / CLARIN / OEAW.** - Focuses on expanding the CLARIN central catalogue into a Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) and integrating it with FAIR assessment tools. This pilot aligns with OSTrails' objectives of enhancing metadata enrichment and data interoperability within the humanities and social sciences.
- **T7 - ENVRI / LifeWatch ERIC.** - Integrates multiple environmental data sources into federated searches, emphasizing semantic integration with LifeBlock and the development of SKGs. The pilot also incorporates maDMPs to automate and improve data management practices in the environmental domain.
- **T8 - SSHOC / CLARIN.** - Extends existing data catalogues into SKGs and enhances interoperability within OSTrails. The pilot works on aligning data models and vocabularies, contributing to the improvement of data management and FAIR assessment in the social sciences and humanities.
- **T9 - ESCAPE / ObsParis.** - Focuses on astronomy data management, specifically with the MASER portal and Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory (CTAO). The pilot aims

to adopt maDMP tools, integrate with SKGs, and implement FAIR assessment criteria tailored to astronomy datasets.

Below, we present a brief summary about the objective of each of the pilot inside the OSTrails project:

5.3. T-1: FAIRsharing for ESFRI Science Clusters

Pilot Number & Title	T-1. FAIRsharing Pilot
Key organisations	University of Oxford, and all RIs and organisations in the five Science Clusters (EOSC-Life, ESCAPE, ENVRI, PANOSC, SSHOC).
Objectives	Enrich FAIRsharing as a collaborative resource for community standards, databases, and policies, enhancing the integration with DMPs, FAIR assessment and assistance tools, and SKGs.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	Core standards, data resources, and policies are integral to RDM tasks.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	FAIRsharing enables the FAIR Principles by promoting the value and the use of standards (for data and metadata), databases and policies.
Involvement in EOSC	FAIRsharing is an RDA-endorsed output, it is also recommended in several EOSC reports, policies, as well as funding programmes' guidance to applicants; FAIRsharing is also connected and used by many other EOSC resources.
Description of Activities	Working with and for all the five ESFRI Science Clusters, this pilot focuses on the collaborative enrichment of FAIRsharing , a resource of interlinked community standards (to identify and report data and metadata), databases (repositories and knowledge bases), and policies (from all organisations). FAIRsharing content will power DMP tools and FAIR assistance services to find and extract relevant standards and databases for inclusion in DMPs, or for FAIRness validation processes. This pilot will leverage the concept of FAIRsharing Collections, which are specific views of the content and its relationships, and that can be customised according to the needs and focus of the creator (a cluster, a RI, or a single organisation; e.g. collection of standards in astronomy https://fairsharing.org/IVOA by ESCAPE, and its related graph https://fairsharing.org/graph/3515). To enable this collaborative work, the FAIRsharing Community

	<p>Champions Programme will ensure formal representation of all Science Clusters and their research infrastructures, crediting their individual and organisational contributions via the use of ORCID and ROR.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contribution to FAIRness assessment, assistance, DMP creation, and SKGs enrichment. • Integration of FAIRsharing content with OSTrails components for enhanced interoperability across science clusters.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of records and Collections, and the number of RIs engaged via the Community Champion programme⁸ • Increased discovery of standards and databases by DMPs and FAIR assessment and assistance tools.
Pilot activities	Timeline
Continuous involvement through the FAIRsharing Community Champions Programme.	Until end of project

5.4. T-2: PaNOSC / ESRF, SOLEIL, ILL

Pilot Number & Title	T-2: PaNOSC / ESRF, SOLEIL, ILL
Key organisations	<p>The PaNOSC pilot, involving ESRF and SOLEIL, focuses on implementing automated generation of maDMPs and expanding this capability across the Photon and Neutron communities. This directly supports OSTrails' ambition to transform DMPs from static documents into living, interconnected resources that are fully aligned with FAIR principles. Although the pilot is still developing its RDM policy, it is already engaged in EOSC, which positions it well for integrating into the OSTrails framework. One of the key challenges identified is the adaptation of existing DMP templates into dynamic maDMPs, which will be essential for the automated assessment processes that OSTrails aims to implement. The anticipated outcome is enhanced quality and</p>

⁸ The FAIRsharing Community Champions Programme is a community of domain and discipline experts who (i) act as advocates to promote the value of standards, databases and policies for digital objects (incl. data, software) (ii), create educational material describing these resources helping researchers and other stakeholders to find, use and adopt them and (iii) enrich the content of FAIRsharing, adding and enhancing the description and discoverability of these resources. See https://fairsharing.org/community_champions

	visibility of datasets and publications from Photon and Neutron facilities, which will contribute to the OSTrails goal of improving research data management across different scientific domains.
Objectives	Implement automatic generation of ma-DMPs and foster deployment across the Photon and Neutrons community.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	No current RDM policy, but there is interest in development.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Aim to improve dataset FAIRness with enhanced metadata and integration of FAIRness assessment tools.
Involvement in EOSC	Active in EOSC through involvement in relevant projects.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enhancing DMP templates, repository integration, and establishing links with SKGs. Alignment with FAIR metrics for the community.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update of datasets metadata and creation of a maDMP template for institutional assessment.
Pilot activities and Timeline	
Integration and implementation of required components, followed by user engagement and testing.	

5.5. T-3: ENVRI / JERICO

Pilot Number & Title	T-3: ENVRI / JERICO
Key organisations	The ENVRI / JERICO pilot, with SOCIB as key organization, is focused on extending the JERICO e-infrastructure to integrate DMPs, datasets, and other digital objects, which is in line with OSTrails' objective of creating a comprehensive, interconnected ecosystem for research data management. This pilot is actively involved in the EOSC through the Blue-Cloud initiative, which aims to integrate marine data into a wider research framework. Although the pilot currently lacks a formal RDM policy, it recognizes the need to develop dynamic DMP templates that

	align with the OSTrails framework, specifically by choosing metadata schemas that are compliant with OSTrails interoperability requirements. The outcome from this pilot is expected to be an interoperable schema for SKGs, enhancing the monitoring and reporting capabilities within the OSTrails infrastructure.
Objectives	Develop an interoperable SKG schema and improve data monitoring and reporting.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	Ongoing, with a focus on transitioning from static to living maDMPs.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Strong focus on integrating FAIR principles into SKGs and enhancing dataset FAIRness.
Involvement in EOSC	Active participant in EOSC through projects like Blue-Cloud 2026.
Affiliation with National Funders	Linked to Spanish and Balearic Islands' governmental bodies.
Description of Activities	Development of maDMPs and integration with SKGs, with a focus on coastal data and services.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	Testing maDMP templates and assessing data quantity and quality.
Pilot activities and Timeline	
Early adaptation of templates, integration with repositories, and contribution to SKG interoperability.	

5.6. T-4: CLARIN, CESSDA, PaNOSC

This pilot involved a cross-domain activity focused on improving metadata and infrastructure quality of thematic services specifically targeting standardisation in terminology and compliance across clusters. However, with the start of the project, the clusters-initiated coordination meetings among them making the standardisation activity a core of their common efforts. For that, the pilot is discontinued, and the resources will

be repurposed for clusters' coordination in OSTrails and their representation in RDA to enhance the SKG-IF model with thematic metadata and entities.

5.7. T-5: SSHOC/CESSDA

Pilot Number & Title	T-5: SSHOC/CESSDA
Key organisations	<p>The SSHOC/CESSDA pilot, with key organisations CESSDA ERIC, CESSDA/FSD, CESSDA/UKDS, focuses on enhancing the interoperability and FAIRness of social science datasets. This pilot is centred around adapting existing CESSDA tools to align with the OSTrails framework, specifically by integrating with the DMP Interoperability Framework (DMP IF) and developing APIs to ensure seamless interaction between DMPs and the CESSDA SKG, the CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS) as well as the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST). Also adding information from other SKGs into the CESSDA SKG will be tested. The pilot aims to enhance the metadata quality and interoperability of social science datasets across repositories, thus improving their discoverability and reusability.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Adapt the CESSDA SKG, the CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS) and the European Language Social Science Thesaurus (ELSST) to comply with the DMP Interoperability Framework (DMP IF). ● Develop and integrate APIs for SKG, CVS and ELSST for use in DMP tools and repositories. ● Create a validation test to check the presence of required elements and validate content. ● Incorporate OSTrails FAIR Assessment Tests into the CESSDA Metadata Validator, flagging datasets by their assessed FAIRness levels. ● Prototype/test to improve CESSDA SKG metadata with information available from other SKGs e.g. related publications
RDM Policy Implementation Status	CESSDA is working on enhancing metadata validation against DDI specifications and local CESSDA Metadata Models.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Strong commitment to ensuring standardised metadata, interoperability, and enhancing data reusability through

	controlled vocabularies and the DMP Interoperability Framework.
Involvement in EOSC	CESSDA ERIC is actively involved in thematic developments as part of a potential EOSC Node through SSHOC.
Affiliation with National Funders	Not explicitly mentioned, but collaboration with Finnish, Norwegian, and Croatian national pilots is planned.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adapting and developing the CESSDA SKG, the CESSDA Vocabulary Service (CVS) and ELSST to align with the DMP IF. • Developing and integrating APIs for SKG and controlled vocabularies into DMP tools and repositories. • Testing the CESSDA SKG metadata enrichment using the information available from other SKGs • Implementing a validation test for social science datasets to ensure compliance with required metadata elements. • Integrating OSTrails FAIR Assessment Tests within the CESSDA Metadata Validator. • Validating harvested dataset metadata against DDI specifications and the CESSDA Metadata Model.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Number of DMPs assessed. 2. Number of datasets assessed. 3. Number of new DMPs using the CESSDA vocabularies 4. Number of new DMPs informing the reuse of the data archived in CESSDA SP (data found from the CESSDA SKG) 5. Number of new datasets deposited using the new metadata element. 6. Adoption rate of APIs by DMP tools and repositories. 7. Number of information items harvested from other SKGs and added into CESSDA SKG 8. Improvement in dataset FAIRness scores.
Pilot activities and Timeline	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The pilot has not yet finalised a detailed timeline but plans to include a dedicated webinar to showcase the pilot's implementation and promote stakeholder engagement. 	

- Continuous collaboration with OSTrails national pilots and DMP tools developers.
- Development of a "Test set" for social science datasets and validation of metadata against local CESSDA models.

5.8. T-6: SSHOC / CLARIN / OEAW

Pilot Number & Title	T-6: SSHOC / CLARIN / OEAW
Key organisations	The SSHOC / CLARIN / OEAW pilot, with key organisation OEAW, aims to extend the central catalogue of European CLARIN into a Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) and integrate FAIR assessment tools, aligning closely with OSTrails' mission to enhance the interoperability and assessment of research data. Active participation in EOSC through SSHOC indicates this pilot's strategic importance in advancing FAIR principles within the humanities and social sciences. The pilot has identified the need for better integration between catalogues and SKGs, which will be critical for achieving OSTrails' goals of seamless data management and assessment across different research outputs. The pilot's work on metadata enrichment and interoperability will contribute significantly to the OSTrails objective of creating an interconnected, FAIR-compliant research ecosystem.
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extend the CLARIN central catalogue into an SKG and integrate it with the OSTrails framework.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	Currently in the testing phase with existing tools like DSW, DAMAP, and ARGOS.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Commitment to integrating FAIR principles in the SKG and ensuring proper metadata enrichment.
Involvement in EOSC	Active in EOSC through thematic projects.
Affiliation with National Funders	National CLARIN consortia are funded by national funders.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of SKGs with FAIR assessments and development of community-specific FAIR metrics.

Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Expansion of the SKG with access to FAIR assessment tools and strong links to other SKGs.
Pilot activities and Timeline	
Ongoing testing and adaptation of tools for community-specific needs.	

5.9. T-7: ENVRI/LifeWatch ERIC

Pilot Number & Title	T-7: ENVRI/LifeWatch ERIC
Key organisations	<p>The ENVRI/LifeWatch ERIC thematic pilot, with key organisations LifeWatch ERIC, ENVRI, is at the forefront of integrating multiple sources of environmental data into federated searches, particularly focusing on the seamless integration of databases within the ENVRI infrastructure. This integration is essential for enabling comprehensive data discovery and enhancing the interoperability of environmental research data. A significant aspect of this pilot is its emphasis on the semantic integration of LifeBlock information, which is already well-developed. As a result, a key priority for this pilot is the advancement of Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), which are crucial for ensuring that the integrated data is not only accessible but also meaningfully connected and interoperable.</p> <p>The pilot also places a strong emphasis on incorporating machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) into its objectives. By transitioning from traditional, static DMPs to dynamic, machine-actionable versions, this pilot aims to enhance the automation, interoperability, and FAIR compliance of research data management processes within the environmental research domain.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and implement an interoperable data management framework that supports maDMPs tailored for environmental research, with a particular focus on biodiversity and ecosystem data. Enhance the FAIRness of digital objects within the LifeWatch and ENVRI infrastructures by integrating with OSTrails tools and methodologies, particularly focusing on Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). Foster interoperability across environmental data repositories through federated searches, ensuring

	seamless data exchange and compliance with FAIR principles.
RDM Policy Implementation Status	The pilot is refining its Research Data Management (RDM) policies, with a strong emphasis on transitioning from traditional DMPs to dynamic, machine-actionable DMPs that align with the OSTrails framework.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	The pilot demonstrates a strong commitment to the FAIR principles, with specific efforts to enhance metadata quality, integrate with SKGs, and ensure that all data outputs are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.
Involvement in EOSC	LifeWatch ERIC and ENVRI are both actively involved in the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), contributing to various projects that aim to standardise and improve data management practices across Europe’s environmental research community.
Affiliation with National Funders	The pilot is connected to multiple national and European funding bodies, which support the broader environmental research initiatives under LifeWatch and ENVRI.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of maDMPs tailored to environmental research, with a focus on biodiversity and ecosystem data. • Integration of environmental data repositories with the OSTrails infrastructure, including the development of interoperable SKGs and federated search capabilities. • Alignment of data management practices with FAIR principles, including the development of community-specific FAIR assessment metrics.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful development and deployment of maDMP templates across the LifeWatch and ENVRI infrastructures. • Increase in the number of datasets and digital objects within LifeWatch and ENVRI repositories that are fully compliant with FAIR principles. • Expansion of SKGs to include comprehensive environmental data, enhancing their interoperability and

	discoverability through federated searches within the OSTrails framework.
Pilot activities	Timeline
Refinement of RDM policies, development of maDMP templates, and the integration of semantic metadata	Early stages
Activities focus on the integration of SKGs with existing data repositories and the alignment of metadata practices with OSTrails standards	Mid-term
Full implementation of FAIR assessment tools, continuous enhancement of data interoperability, development of federated search capabilities across the LifeWatch and ENVRI networks	Long-term

5.10. T-8: SSHOC / CLARIN

Pilot Number & Title	T-8: SSHOC / CLARIN
Key organisations	This SSHOC / CLARIN pilot, with key organisation KNAW/HuC, focuses on extending existing data catalogues into SKGs and enhancing their interoperability within the OSTrails framework. The pilot is actively involved in national and thematic open science initiatives, which aligns with OSTrails' goal of fostering a collaborative and interoperable research data management ecosystem. The pilot has identified the need for better alignment of data models and vocabularies between catalogues and SKGs, which is critical for achieving the OSTrails objective of creating an interconnected and FAIR-compliant research infrastructure. The expected outcome includes the expansion of SKGs with access to FAIR assessments, contributing to the OSTrails mission of enhancing the quality and interoperability of research data.
Objectives	Extend the CLARIN central catalogue into a Scientific Knowledge Graph (SKG) and integrate it with the OSTrails framework to facilitate better data management and accessibility.

RDM Policy Implementation Status	In progress, with testing of existing tools like DSW, DAMAP, and ARGOS to determine the best fit for the pilot's needs.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	The pilot is committed to ensuring that the SKG adheres to FAIR principles, particularly through metadata enrichment and integration of FAIR assessment tools.
Involvement in EOSC	Active in EOSC through thematic projects like SSHOC and broader participation in EOSC-related initiatives.
Affiliation with National Funders	The pilot is linked to national funders through the national CLARIN consortia.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focused on the expansion of the central catalogue into an SKG with strong connections to other SKGs and access to FAIR assessment tools/reports. • Integration of community-specific FAIR metrics and alignment with the OSTrails interoperability framework.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successfully extending the SKG with robust links to other SKGs and integrating FAIR assessment capabilities tailored to the needs of the social sciences and humanities.

Pilot activities and Timeline	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ongoing involvement in shaping the SKG IF and FAIR assessment • Ongoing activities include testing and adapting tools for community-specific requirements, with an emphasis on enhancing data management practices within the SKG framework. • Starting up the work to make the joined metadata of the VLO (CLARIN's central catalogue) a suitable basis for a SKG. • Implement the SKG IF making the CLARIN SKG OSTrails compliant. <p>Ultimately extend the VLO to give its users access to the network of SKGs and FAIR assessment (reports).</p>	

5.11. T-9: ESCAPE / ObsParis

Pilot Number & Title	T-9: ESCAPE / ObsParis
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<p>Key organisations</p>	<p>The ESCAPE / ObsParis pilot, with key organisation Observatoire de Paris, is focused on implementing OSTrails solutions to enhance data management and FAIR compliance in the astronomy domain. It is based on two main sub use-cases to explore various practices in astronomy: the MASER (Measuring, Analysing & Simulating Emissions in the Radio range) portal that is offering access to a series of tools and databases linked to low frequency radio astronomy; and the CTAO (Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory) that aims at developing tools for gamma-ray astronomy and enhancing the FAIRness of the data produced by the CTAO and High Energy observatories in general.</p> <p>The pilot is already active in EOSC through the ESCAPE and FAIR-IMPACT projects and participates in the IVOA (International Virtual Observatory Alliance) that fosters data interoperability in the astronomy domain. The pilot is in the process of developing its RDM policy, with the aim of aligning it with international Open Science standards. One of the challenges identified is the need to adapt existing tools to meet the specific requirements of the astronomy community, which reflects OSTrails' goal of creating customizable, community-specific solutions. The expected outcome is the development of interfaces compatible with SKGs and the proposal of FAIR assessment criteria tailored to the needs of the astronomy domain, contributing to OSTrails' broader objective of advancing FAIRness across various scientific disciplines.</p>
<p>Objectives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Use OSTrails to enhance the MASER service, focusing on repository and toolbox integration (including all OSTRAILS toolbox: DMP, SKG and FAIR assessment): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ DMP: adopt a maDMP tool and integrate the DMP database in the data publication process. ○ SKG: provide / retrieve metadata using OSTRAILS SKG API, for data preparation, publication and impact monitoring ○ FAIR: include FAIR assessment in data preparation and publication process ● CTAO: Enhance the DMP using DMP tools and improve metadata interfaces with SKGs. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Develop DMP policy for CTAO, to serve as a use case for maDMP tools ○ Prototype implementation of dataset provenance metadata in SKG

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Integrate and test FAIR assessment criteria
RDM Policy Implementation Status	Policy in progress, with current focus on moving from manual DMP management to maDMP platform.
Commitment to FAIR Principles	Strong, with an emphasis on publishing datasets with rich metadata and adherence to community standards.
Involvement in EOSC	Active participant in EOSC projects (ESCAPE and FAIR-IMPACT), and in the EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability Task Force, and two projects funded by OSCARS cascading grants (OPAL and ASTRO-CC). Participants are also members of the “Collège EOSC France”, which is the national working group for the national EOSC participation.
Affiliation with National Funders	Affiliated with national institutions like CNRS.
Description of Activities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Development of DMPs using maDMP platforms (currently testing DSW) ● integration with SKGs (mapping with astronomy metadata standards, participating in the RDA SKG-IF WG) ● alignment with FAIR assessment tools, and specifically to prepare a FAIR profile for astronomy datasets.
Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SKGs enrichment with new entities (like usable access information), ● Integration of a maDMP platform for producing DMPs ● 1000 FAIR assessed digital objects ● 1 institution engaged
Pilot activities and Timeline	
Focus on integrating SKGs with existing repositories and refining data management practices.	

6. Horizon Europe Pilot

6.1. Overview / Background

In Horizon Europe, beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles, and are required to at least do the following:

- Prepare a Data Management Plan (DMP) and keep it updated throughout the course of the project.
- Deposit data in a trusted repository and provide open access to it ('as open as possible, as closed as necessary').
- Provide information (via the same repository) about any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to re-use or validate the data.

Data Management Plans: All Horizon Europe projects are required to create a Data Management Plan (DMP) within 6 months after the start of the project. The DMP is a living document that outlines how research data will be handled during and after the project. It covers aspects such as data collection, storage, sharing, and preservation. The DMP must be updated regularly to reflect any changes in data management practices or project needs.

Open Access and FAIR Data: Horizon Europe promotes the principle of 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary.' This means that while data should generally be open and accessible, exceptions are made for privacy, confidentiality/competitiveness, or security concerns. Moreover, data should adhere to the FAIR principles.

Ethical and Legal Compliance: Data management in Horizon Europe must comply with all relevant ethical and legal requirements, including GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) for personal data. Projects must ensure that data handling practices are ethical, particularly when dealing with sensitive or personal information. Proper consent mechanisms, anonymization, and data security measures are essential components of this compliance.

Data Sharing and Repositories: Horizon Europe encourages the use of established, trusted repositories for data sharing. Data should be deposited in repositories that provide long-term access and preservation. Data should be shared under open licences (CC-BY, or equivalent, CC-O statement) that allow for broad reuse, while still respecting intellectual property rights and confidentiality agreements.

6.2. Plans and Activities

The OSTrails project aims to advance DMP evaluation practices and support adherence to Research Data Management (RDM) policies by following the proposed PTA framework. The Horizon Europe pilot positions the adoption of OSTrails results at larger scale to support project officers in their duties with respect to evaluating DMPs and to provide

better tools and workflows for beneficiaries to implement data management practices according to Horizon Europe conditions.

Input from the research community will be sought through surveys and interviews developed in the context of the DMP evaluation service (WP3) and the policy brief (WP6). Both the input and the outputs of those activities, i.e. analysis report on current DMPs in HE projects and a proposed updated DMP template for FP10, will inform the Horizon Europe pilot to:

- 1) Develop the machine actionable template for Horizon Europe DMPs.
- 2) Embed FAIR metrics in the machine actionable template to assess the FAIRness of their described outputs and activities.
- 3) Embed DMP metrics in the machine actionable template for DMPs to be evaluated in a semi-automated way.
- 4) Enhance the machine actionable template with semantics so that qualified references of DMPs with other research outputs can be created.
- 5) Expose maDMPs (.json) along with the .pdf version of the project's DMP deliverables.
- 6) Seek extra configurations with the EC portal.

Our methodology builds on the data collection of EC projects that is available and linked to project's outputs in the OpenAIRE Graph. From this collection, Horizon Europe projects that have finished or are ongoing and should have a DMP will be identified. A first quantitative analysis will be performed on this sample to determine the FAIRness of data that they have produced and the percentage of machine-actionable DMPs currently available. Anonymization of closed access DMPs will be applied if they are deemed necessary for this activity, provided that they are sourced from internal or protected platforms that the project has outreach to (e.g. OSTrails service providers). A subset of the sample's ongoing projects will be invited to participate in the OSTrails pilot and adopt the project's results. To enable these project's DMPs to be machine actionable, ARGOS will onboard and upgrade them to the new and extended Horizon Europe maDMP template that follows RDA's DCS, and specifications developed in WP1-3. FAIR Metrics will also be embedded in the template utilising the results from WP3 via the OpenAIRE FAIR Validator. A comparison analysis of practices before and after the participation to OSTrails will bring to light common challenges and obstacles that prevent DMPs from being machine-actionable or data from being FAIR.

The pilot will collaborate with [TIER2](#) that is developing a Reproducibility Management Plan to enhance current DMPs with reproducibility elements (eg questions and guidance) and combine insights, best practices, and recommendations for improving DMP templates from feedback collected by HE project participants about their experience with the current EC-provided DMP template.

KPIs: 1 maDMP template for Horizon Europe 2 Universities and their researchers engaged; 1000 FAIR assessed digital objects.

Timeline and Implementation Activities:

maDMP template, adaptation and evaluation: March 2025 - March 2026

Assessment of digital objects, including deployment of assessment tool: March 2025 - December 2025

7. Cross Pilot and Cross Project Activities Coordination

7.1. Intra-Pilot Coordination

One of the key objectives of our work is to ensure clear role distribution and streamlined collaboration within each national and thematic pilot. National and thematic pilot often consist of multiple partners; it is therefore important to have a well-defined coordination structure within each pilot. This involves:

- **Role Allocation:** Identifying which partner will lead specific tasks or use cases. This includes assigning responsibilities for developing, testing, and validating solutions within the pilot.
- **Regular Communication:** Setting up regular internal meetings within each pilot to discuss progress, address challenges, and refine strategies. This also involves ensuring that all partners are aligned on objectives and timelines.
- **Documentation and Reporting:** Establishing a clear process for documenting progress and outcomes. This ensures transparency and accountability within the pilot and provides valuable insights for other pilots.

This will be integrated in the project reporting; pilots will also report in the monthly meetings.

7.2. Inter-Pilot Coordination

Another crucial aspect of our work is fostering collaboration and knowledge exchange between a) the different national pilots and thematic pilots respectively, and b) exchange information and knowledge that is relevant to both national and thematic pilots.

While each pilot operates independently, there are significant benefits to be gained from cross-pilot collaboration, such as sharing best practice and joint problem solving, tool testing as well as interacting with the other work packages (see also 7.3.).

7.2.1 Process for national pilots

Representatives from each national pilot come together on a monthly basis to share updates, challenges, and successes. These (already ongoing) meetings have a structured agenda, covering at least the following points:

- ongoing developments from the technical activities of the project (represented by OSTrails technical manager).
- presentation of a specific tool and invitation to pilots to test it (based on the work performed in other WP activities, e.g. tools' flashcards).
- updates from the national pilots on their progress and achievements: events, activities, best practices, challenges - also for discussion with the other national pilots.

7.2.2 Process for thematic pilots

Thematic pilots within OSTrails serve partly as specialised testbeds where advanced methodologies and tools developed in WP1, WP2, and WP3 will be tested and validated within specific scientific domains. Additionally, they provide new community infrastructures that can be further integrated in the existing infrastructure. Given the diversity of thematic pilots, it is critical to establish a coordination mechanism that ensures both alignment in the coordination of the tools with the pilots and adaptability to the unique needs of each pilot.

This will be done through the following actions:

1. **Thematic Pilots Coordination Committee (TPCC):**
 - Establish a TPCC comprising representatives from each thematic pilot. The TPCC will be responsible for overseeing the progress, ensuring adherence to OSTrails' goals, and facilitating cross-pilot learning. communication.
 - Monthly TPCC meetings will focus on discussing progress, challenges, and innovations within each pilot. The agenda will include updates on tool developments from WP1 (interoperability and infrastructure), WP2 (tool integration and implementation), and WP3 (FAIR metrics and assessment tools).
2. **Integration with WP1, WP2, and WP3:**

The thematic pilot communities are directly involved in the co-creation process started in terms of OSTrails Deliverable 1.1: Plan-Track-Assess Pathways (Reichmann et al., 2024), where they provided valuable input. Deliverable 1.1 represents the first technical deliverable of the project, focused on identifying and co-designing the Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) framework and its pathways (i.e., PTA pathways). The PTA framework serves as a high-level, tool-independent structure

that guides researchers, research managers, and funders in planning, tracking, and assessing the management of Digital Objects (DO) in alignment with the FAIR Guiding Principles. The framework's primary components include Data Management Plans (DMPs), Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs), and FAIR assessment tools. To develop the PTA pathways, conceptual diagrams of these components were created based on input from consortium service providers and validated by the project's thematic pilots.

- **WP1 Integration:** The thematic pilot communities are already participating in WP1 discussing and creating interoperability framework and the pilots will integrate advanced interoperability frameworks and Scientific Knowledge Graphs (SKGs). Each pilot will work on aligning its community data models and infrastructures with the OSTRails Interoperability Reference Architecture (IRA), ensuring that data and metadata from different sources are seamlessly integrated and interoperable across the broader OSTRails ecosystem.
 - **WP2 Integration:** The thematic pilot communities participated in the development of tools and services, and in the pilot, phase will be testing and refine them. This includes implementing machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) tailored to the specific needs of each thematic community. Pilots will provide feedback on the usability and effectiveness of these tools, contributing to iterative improvements.
 - **WP3 Integration:** The thematic pilot communities participated in the development of FAIR metrics and assessment tools and the pilots will apply and evaluate them. Each pilot will be responsible for customising and testing these tools within their domain, ensuring that they meet the specific requirements of the scientific community involved. This will involve close collaboration with WP3 to refine and adapt metrics to ensure they accurately reflect the FAIRness of the digital objects within each thematic area.
3. **Cross-Pilot Tool Testing and Knowledge Exchange:**
- **Tool Testing:** Thematic pilots will be encouraged to participate in cross-pilot tool testing sessions, where they can test tools developed by other pilots or relevant to other domains. This fosters a collaborative environment where best practices and successful strategies can be shared across different scientific domains.
 - **Knowledge Exchange:** Regular knowledge exchange meetings will be held where thematic pilots present their progress, challenges, and findings. These workshops will be designed to identify synergies and potential areas for collaboration between pilots. For example, a pilot focusing on

environmental data integration might collaborate with a social sciences pilot to explore cross-domain interoperability.

4. Documentation and Reporting:

- Each thematic pilot will maintain documentation of its activities, including the integration of tools, challenges faced, and outcomes achieved. This documentation will be shared with the TPCC and the broader OSTrails consortium to ensure transparency and to contribute to the overall body of knowledge within the project.
- Thematic pilots will also submit quarterly reports to the WP4 leadership team, summarising their progress and highlighting any issues that require attention or support from other work packages.

5. Alignment with OSTrails Deliverables and Milestones:

- Thematic pilots will work closely with the WP4 leadership team to ensure that their activities align with the overall OSTrails deliverables and milestones. This includes ensuring that all thematic pilot outputs are validated against the OSTrails objectives, particularly the development of interoperable, machine-actionable research data management solutions that are FAIR-compliant.
- Pilot outcomes will be assessed against predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to ensure they contribute effectively to the project's goals. These KPIs will include metrics such as the number of SKGs integrated, the adoption rate of maDMPs, and the improvement in FAIR assessment scores within the pilot domains.

6. Feedback and Continuous Improvement:

- A feedback loop will be established where thematic pilots provide ongoing input to WP1, WP2, and WP3 on the tools and methodologies they are testing. This feedback will be used to refine and improve the tools, ensuring they are fit-for-purpose and meet the needs of the scientific communities involved in OSTrails.
- Thematic pilots will also participate in evaluation sessions where their progress and outcomes are reviewed by the broader OSTrails consortium. This ensures that lessons learned are shared and that successful strategies can be adopted by other pilots.

7.2.3 Process for Horizon Europe Pilot

The Horizon Europe Pilot will report twice yearly in joint meetings with all pilots. These meetings will provide an opportunity to share progress, challenges, and lessons learned, facilitating cross-pilot knowledge exchange and collaboration. The Horizon makes use of some of the tools developed by the technical work packages 1-3.

7.2.4 Process for joint issues

The thematic pilot and the Horizon Europe pilot are invited to join the monthly national pilots meeting on specific occasions, e.g. for sharing recent developments in their areas. Such joint pilot meetings will be held at least twice a year.

7.3. Cross-Work Package Coordination

Special attention is given on cross WP communication to ensure that the developments from technical activities are effectively integrated into the pilots and that pilots provide valuable feedback to these activities and results.

Coordination between the pilots and the technical activities performed in WP1-3 is crucial for the successful implementation of shared solutions. This coordination involves:

- **Early Involvement of Pilots:** Engaging pilots early in the development process of tools and solutions being developed by the technical work packages. This ensures that the solutions are aligned with the needs of the pilots and can be adapted based on pilot feedback.
- **Regular Updates and Feedback Loops:** Work packages 1, 2, and 3 are invited to participate in the pilots meeting to provide regular updates on their developments, and pilots offer feedback based on their practical experiences.
- **Output presentations:** WP5 will organise meetings where specific deliverables are presented to the consortium once they are finished.
- **Participation in project meetings:** The pilot representatives and the WP4 leadership team are present and engaged in the regular consortium management meetings, such as the monthly online project strategic meeting (PSC) and the annual in person project meetings.

Conclusions

The national, thematic, and Horizon Europe pilots play a critical role in the overall success of OSTrails by showcasing a diverse array of research environments, each with distinct challenges, goals, and infrastructure capabilities. This reflects the broad spectrum of Research Data Management (RDM) practices across Europe and various scientific disciplines. Serving as testing grounds for RDM solutions developed in the project, these pilots evaluate the effectiveness of the Plan-Track-Assess (PTA) framework and provide valuable feedback that drives the iterative development process.

By actively engaging local stakeholders and aligning with the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), the pilots contribute to building a more integrated and FAIR-compliant research ecosystem. National pilots, for instance, are focusing on developing machine-actionable Data Management Plans (maDMPs) and enhancing interoperability between local research infrastructures. Thematic pilots support these efforts by working on knowledge graphs and FAIR assessment tools. The Horizon Europe pilot scales adoption of OSTrails results to support the EC RDM policy.

In this broader context, the pilots are essential in transforming how research data is managed, shared, and made FAIR across Europe. Their continuous feedback loops and collaboration with technical work packages ensure that OSTrails remains aligned with both local needs and the overall vision of a more interconnected and FAIR-enhanced research landscape.

8. References

- Reichmann, S., Rey Mazón, M., Hasani-Mavriqi, I., Thaci, L., Eckhard, D., 2024. D1.1: Plan-Track-Assess Pathways. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.13145787>
- Science Europe, 2020. Implementing Research Data Management Policies Across Europe: Experiences from Science Europe Member Organisations. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.4915951>

9. Annex: Survey Template

This annex contains screenshots of the excel files used in the survey conducted with the aim to initially identify a) the respective pilots' ecosystem in which they operate and b) the use cases/topics that they intend to work on. The survey contains two main worksheets:

- worksheet 1 - overview of use cases/topics with the aim to elicit from each pilot whether they are at the time of writing: a) sure that they will cover a use case b) uncertain that they will cover a use case, c) sure that they will not cover a use case and d) other options, such as covering a use case through their own resources ("in kind").
- worksheet 2 - 26 structured questions covering the participating origins policies and activities regarding RDM and FAIRification, as well as the wider national or thematic community in which they operate.

9.1. Worksheet 1 – Use cases overview

Topics/User Cases (from DoW)	1-Croatia Ruzic Bookovic Institute	2-Greece Hellenic Academic Libraries Link members, athena RC	3-Netherlands SURF	4-Norway Sikt	5-Serbia U Belgrade	6-Austria- Uni Wien, TU Wien, TU Graz	7-Poland PSNC, U Warsaw/KCM	8-Ireland TU Dublin	9-Portugal U of Minho	10-france (INRIA)	11-Finland CSC	12-Germany RWTH Aachen	13-Spain FECYT	14-Czech Republic, CTU
I develop maDMP templates to address national funders and local infrastructure (PIDs, ORs, repositories);						x								
II extend repositories for archiving maDMPs and create links and relations (qualified references) between archived DMPs and publications;						x								
III Integrate with the OpenAIRE Graph or other SKOs to enhance qualified references with publications (incl. Pre-prints, open peer reviews), DMPs, maFAIRTests, data, workflows, instruments, software;						optional in kind								
IV co-define FAIR metrics for funders, institutions and research communities and assess deposited DO's and repositories;						?								
V co-define DMP evaluation criteria and assess DMPs quality according to national policy and criteria.						x								
VI extend national monitoring systems and funder's reporting systems with maDMPs						o								

9.2. Worksheet 2 – Eco system analysis

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#	Questionnaire Element	Description	Relevant for WP
1	Pilot Type	Identify if the pilot is national or thematic.	WP4
2	Pilot Name	Name of the pilot	WP4
3	Pilot members and role/responsibilities	Organizations participating in it, mention thematic cluster if relevant	WP4
5	Short Description	A brief description of the pilot (100 words)	WP4
6	RDM (research data management) Policy Implementation Status related to the doing so?		WP4
7	Commitment to FAIR	Does the organization want to strengthen FAIR principles, and how?	WP4
8	Involvement in EOSC	Are the pilot members active in national or thematic EOSC developments?	WP4
9	Affiliation with National Funders (if relevant)	Is the national pilot affiliated with national funders?	WP4
10	Identification of Local Infrastructure Gaps	pillars?	WP1,WP2
11	Required Components for End-to-End Solutions	WPs?	WP1,WP2
12	Characteristics of Local or Community Requirements	What does the local community need to assess outputs and DMP?	WP3
13	Experience with Assessment Methods for outputs and DMPs.	methods?	WP3
14	Testing and Evaluation of Methods, Tools, and Services	services? (if yes please describe briefly)	WP2, WP3
15	Interaction with OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs	How does the organization interact with OpenAIRE Graph or other SKGs?	WP4
16	Development of maDMP Templates	addressing local infrastructure and funding bodies?	WP4
17	Archiving of maDMPs	outputs?	WP4
18	Co-definition of FAIR Metrics	stakeholders?	WP4
19	Evaluation of Deposited DOs and Repositories	repositories?	WP4
20	DMP Evaluation Criteria	national policy?	WP4
21	Extension of National Monitoring and Funder's Reporting Systems	How monitoring and reporting takes place in your organization?	WP4
22	Expected outcomes	What will you obtain from the pilot and what will the community obtain?	WP5
23	KPIs	How do you plan to accomplish the KPIs of your pilot?	WP5
24	User engagement	for your pilot?	WP5
25	Relevant stakeholders	How do you interact with national or thematic open science communities?	WP5

national pilots Thematic pilots Extended Questionnaire

Ready Accessibility: Good to go

